

Lights All Askew: Systematics in Galaxy Images from Megaparsecs to Microns

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Lights All Askew: Systematics in Galaxy Images from Megaparsecs to Microns

Abstract

The stars and galaxies are not where they seem. In the process of imaging and measurement, the light from distant objects is distorted, blurred, and skewed by several physical effects on scales from megaparsecs to microns. Charge-coupled devices (CCDs) provide sensitive detection of this light, but introduce their own problems in the form of systematic biases. Images of these stars and galaxies are formed in CCDs when incoming light generates photoelectrons which are then collected in a pixel's potential well and measured as signal. However, these signal electrons can be diverted from purely parallel paths toward the pixel wells by transverse fields sourced by structural elements of the CCD, accidental imperfections in fabrication, or dynamic electric fields induced by other collected charges. These charge transport anomalies lead to measurable systematic errors in the images which bias cosmological inferences based on them. The physics of imaging therefore deserves thorough investigation, which is performed in the laboratory using a unique optical beam simulator and in computer simulations of charge transport.

On top of detector systematics, there are often biases in the mathematical analysis of pixelized images; in particular, the location, shape, and orientation of stars and galaxies. Using elliptical Gaussians as a toy model for galaxies, it is demonstrated how small biases in the computed image moments lead to observable orientation patterns in modern survey data. Also presented are examples of the reduction of data and fitting of optical aberrations of images in the lab and on the sky which are modeled by physically or mathematically-motivated methods.

Finally, end-to-end analysis of the weak gravitational lensing signal is presented using deep sky data as well as in N-body simulations. It is demonstrated how measured weak lens shear can be transformed by signal matched filters which aid in the detection of mass overdensities and separate signal from noise. A commonly-used decomposition of shear into two components, E- and B-modes, is thoroughly tested and both modes are shown to be useful in the detection of large scale structure. We find several astrophysical sources of B-mode and explain their apparent origin. The methods presented therefore offer an optimal way to filter weak gravitational shear into maps of large scale structure through the process of cosmic mass cartography.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Nearly a hundred years ago, photographic observation of a handful of nearby galaxies led to the discovery of the expansion of the Universe and the founding of cosmology as a science. Philosophical questions about the origin of the Universe, its composition, and trajectory suddenly became feasible to answer using theories and data. For observational cosmology these data are the result of rays of light which have been traveling from distant galaxies in some cases for billions of light years, collected using mirrors and detectors. Surveys of the sky carefully image each point of light, uncovering new phenomena and cataloging fainter and further objects in the cartography of the cosmos. Recently, fully digital sky surveys enabled by the introduction of electronic imagers such as charge-coupled devices (CCDs) have greatly extended our grasp.

In the last century this catalog of objects has expanded from hundreds of thousands of stars to billions of stars and hundreds of millions of galaxies. In less than a generation perhaps twenty billion stars in our Milky Way and fifty billion observable galaxies may be within reach. However, the exponential growth of imaging datasets drives an increase in statistical precision which in turn demands systematic accuracy. Each new step in survey depth and size must be accompanied by even greater steps in the understanding of its operation and calibration of its analysis. Observational cosmology must therefore concern itself with the details of the imaging detector, all the way down to the electron, and similar levels of care must be taken in the analysis of the images in order to avoid biasing results.

This dissertation will investigate several aspects of CCD surveys of the sky, from the focusing of light on the detector, to the transport of photoelectrons in silicon, to the mapping of the large scale

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structure of galaxies. In it we will proceed up the signal chain from the collection of data, through the analysis of images, to cosmological results. We will first discuss the detector by presenting several laboratory investigations of prototype CCDs alongside simulations of their operation. Several biasing systematic effects are quantified and modeled. Calibrated image analysis, which bridges the detector's measurements to the scientific results, will then be discussed alongside catalogs from modern galaxy surveys. Finally, we discuss the process of cosmic mass cartography, the mapping of the large scale structure of the Universe through weak gravitational lensing of distant galaxies.

1.1 Collecting the light

For an optical astronomer, the charge-coupled device (CCD) is nearly a perfect detector (Mackay, 1986). Though the CCD was originally invented as a tool for storing and moving charge, its usefulness as an imager was soon applied and replaced film in astronomy. Several benefits came with the leap from film to electronic imaging: a nearly 100x increase in sensitivity (quantum efficiency) and linearity, as well as digitized data, and many modifications have helped incrementally improve its performance over the past several decades. However, to achieve the large fields of view with high resolution that were possible with film requires the small CCDs to be mosaiced into focal plane arrays. Over the years, many mosaic cameras have been built to survey the optical sky and a few notable ones are listed in Table 1.1. Each survey has varying goals which range from studies of our solar system to distant supernovae and galaxy surveys, so each survey variously optimizes its width and depth. One such survey, the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST), aims to go both wide and deep by combining a dedicated wide-field 8.4 meter telescope with a camera composed of over 3 billion pixels. Via repeated exposures of the southern sky, this camera will enable mapping of the three dimensional distribution of billions of stars and galaxies. Analysis of the images has the potential to simultaneously characterize the acceleration of the Universe and tomographically map the growth of its mass structure, decreasing statistical errors on measured cosmological parameters to 1% precision and below. This decrease in statistical error puts equally strict new demands on the performance of the CCD at the start of the signal chain. Without precise knowledge of the camera's systematics errors, downstream measurements may be biased, measurements skewed, and new discoveries limited. Therefore, we must understand major CCD

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Table 1.1: CCD surveys of the sky

Survey name	Camera (Megapixels)	Telescope size (m)	Start year	Area (deg²)	Lim. Mag.
TS12	0.16	4	1983	2.5	26
BTC	16	4	1996	(1, 100, 5000)	(26,24,20)
SDSS	150	2.5	2000	15000	22.5
DLS	64	4	2002	20	26
CFHTLS (Wide/Deep)	340	3.5	2003	(150,16)	(25,25.6)
COSMOS (HST)	16	2.4	2006	2	27.2
Pan-STARRS	1,400	4x1.8	2010	30000	22.8
KiDS	300	2.7	2011	1500	24.6
DES	570	4	2013	5000	25
LSST	3,200	6.7	2019	20000	27

systematics using measurements in the lab as well as through simulations of charge transport.

Most collected photons with wavelengths of 300-900 nanometers end their journey somewhere inside of a pure, cold slab of high purity silicon semiconductor about 1 centimeter across and tens to hundreds of microns thick. Most blue photons are converted in the first micron or so, while redder photons can penetrate further before a photoelectric interaction with an electron in the silicon bulk. If it is of great enough energy, absorption of this photon can excite an electron from the valence to conduction band. Conduction band electrons generally follow the vertical electric fields to the bottom of the silicon where they are trapped in one of the million or so gridded potential wells. These potential wells which form the pixels are induced by arrays of metal oxide semiconductor (MOS) capacitors which store the photoelectrons in a region near the surface layer. After the integration is complete, the collected electron image is read out by charge transfer as indicated on the right of Figure 1.1.1. Rows of pixels are shifted in parallel to the serial register where each pixel is then serially read out through an on-chip amplifier. This process for the last pixel in an 8x8 imager is illustrated with arrows in Figure 1.1.1. This low noise amplifier collects and converts the summed electron charge to an analog voltage signal, which is then converted to a digital signal (so-called Analog to Digital Units, or ADU). The final image is thus convoluted by the process of photoelectron generation, transport, collection, transfer, and measurement, and unbiased image analysis must therefore take relevant errors into account. We individually investigate several aspects of this signal chain using lab measurements as well as simulations in Chapter 2.

At UC Davis, we have constructed a novel bench top simulation of the LSST optical beam to

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Figure 1.1.1: Center: a cartoon of an 8x8 pixel imager where light is incident from above (so-called backside illuminated). Black arrows illustrating the sequential parallel clocking of charge from the 8th row to the serial register, and grey arrows representing the movement of charge via the serial clocks which much move charge at 8x the rate. Right: an illustration of the peristaltic transfer of electrons (orange dots) to the right by varying the pattern of high/low voltages on the parallel clocks. Similar clocking is done for the serial clocks, but at a higher transfer rate. Left: a zoom-in of a single pixel showing the three parallel clocks (P1-3, thick black lines) which contain the charge in rows and can be sequentially clocked for charge transfer. Thick red lines indicate the channel stops which are fixed doping implanted regions which contain the charge in their columns.

test the properties of the signal chain on prototypical CCDs (Tyson et al., 2014). A photograph of the setup is shown in Figure 1.1.2. This facility is unique in that it provides a $f/1.23$ beam similar to the LSST optical design, and enables realistic and high-throughput mock-observing. Rapid characterization of LSST CCDs is possible given wide field of view of the optics which allows for pinhole masks to be placed at the object plane rather than single pinholes. With this setup we can individually investigate both static and dynamic systematic errors, as well as investigate camera operation and optimization. In particular we use these pinhole masks to map and measure astrometric errors, those which shift the photoelectrons perpendicularly during charge collection. The static and dynamic patterns of astrometric error are investigated and found to be dependent upon observing conditions such as PSF brightness, wavelength, sky background, and CCD voltages (Bradshaw et al., 2015).

Measurements made in the lab are matched to simulations of CCD operation which take into account these variable observing conditions, providing a physical basis which can be used to infer the microscopic behavior of the CCD's electric fields and transport of photoelectrons. These simulations proceed by numerically solving for the path of photoelectrons at a given location us-

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Figure 1.1.2: The LSST beam simulator at UC Davis. A: cryogenic dewar with CCD mounted a few centimeters behind the input window. B: LSST $f/1.2$ beam simulator optics, where a spot mask with thousands of pinholes can be placed at the object plane. C: Illuminating sphere which scatters input light to provide uniform coverage of optics. D: Precision X/Y/Z stage upon which the CCD is mounted, enabling micron (1/10th of a pixel) dithering capability.

ing Poisson's equation in a discrete volume. However, the accuracy of the solution requires input boundary potentials and charges which have been implanted (Holland et al., 2014), which are difficult to measure on fabricated devices (Lage et al., 2017). Using well motivated estimates and measurements, Figure 1.1.3 shows the path of three different photoelectrons in the bulk of the CCD: one which is directly incident above a collecting potential well of a pixel, and two which are on either side of the boundary between two pixels. The deflection which occurs near the bottom of the well is due to the potential (color shading) which directs the electron toward collection. In practice any transverse motion of the photoelectrons induces an astrometric error which re-maps the pixel's effective collecting area. Therefore one can summarize these astrometric errors by calculating the effective pixel areas and boundaries given the observing conditions. These deformed pixel boundaries can then be fed into next-generation image processing algorithms to remove the effect of any charge transport anomalies.

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Figure 1.1.3: The path of three photoelectrons: one incident above a pixel's potential well (far right, at $15\mu m$), and two at $\sim 10\mu m$ which are at the boundary between the pixels. This illustrates the sensitivity of the simulation to small changes and the method by which effective pixel areas can be determined.

1.2 The analysis of pixelized objects

The images taken in surveys of the sky must be programatically analyzed to find stars and galaxies and measure their position, shape, brightness, and color over time. Automated measurement of these parameters on realistic data is often fraught with many systematic errors which must be taken into account. Our atmosphere blurs, the telescope's optics distort, and cameras muddle and pixelize; clearly the analysis and measurement is working with imperfect and biased data. Therefore, each measurement must be calibrated for these effects to an increasingly precise level to reveal any cosmological information in the analysis.

To begin object measurement, one must separate the signal from the noise; a typical assumption is that stars and galaxies are isolated elliptical Gaussians in a background of Poissonian sky noise. Objects can then be found by first calculating the the mean and variance of most of the pixels (the background sky) to serve as a threshold, then forming connected pixel maps in the process of image segmentation (Jarvis & Tyson (1981), Bertin & Arnouts (1996)). Once objects are found, the values of pixels associated to each object can be used to compute statistics computed upon them which summarize their size, shape, and flux. One set of commonly computed summary statistics are the

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image moments which describe an object's centroid and radial distribution. They are computed by taking weighted averages of pixel image intensities $I(x, y)$, where the weights $w(x, y)$ can be chosen to be pixel values, radial apodized, or some combination thereof:

$$M_{i,j} = \sum_x \sum_y x^i y^j I(x, y) w(x, y). \quad (1.2.1)$$

When the centroid ($M_{10,01}$) is subtracted from the coordinates within the sum these are called centralized moments. Second centralized moments summarize the spatial extent of object profiles, and in the limit of well-sampled Gaussians they are equal to the σ of the distribution. Similarly, third and fourth order moments correspond to the skewness and kurtosis of Gaussian profiles.

The orientation of an object can be inferred from its moments by considering the covariance between the second moments along each axis:

$$\text{cov}[I(x, y)] = \begin{bmatrix} M_{20} & M_{11} \\ M_{11} & M_{02} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.2.2)$$

assuming normalized images. Eigendecomposition of this matrix provides major and minor axes a, b (and axis ratio $r = b/a$) of the image in relation to the measurement axis, defining an orientation angle:

$$\phi = \frac{1}{2} \arctan \frac{2M_{11}}{M_{20} - M_{02}} \quad (1.2.3)$$

or alternatively a complex ellipticity

$$\epsilon = \frac{M_{11} - M_{22} + 2iM_{12}}{M_{11} + M_{22} + 2(M_{11}M_{22} - M_{12}^2)^{1/2}}. \quad (1.2.4)$$

The second moments are directly applicable to cosmology because the axis ratio and orientation (ellipticity) of galaxies is directly related to the weak lensing shear g (Schneider, 2005):

$$|g| = \frac{1 - b/a}{1 + b/a} \quad (1.2.5)$$

Therefore, simple automated analysis of galaxy images enables the direct measurement of mass along the line of sight, where each galaxy provides a noisy estimate of the local shear. The intrinsic noise in

1.3. Cosmology from billions of pixels

galaxy ellipticity measurements is dominated by the random (unlensed) ellipticity of source galaxies $\sigma_\epsilon = \sqrt{\langle \epsilon \epsilon^* \rangle}$. Observing the true unlensed ellipticity dispersion is difficult and often estimated from the weakly lensed ellipticity dispersion, typically measured to be $\sigma_\epsilon \sim 0.3$. This assumed random ellipticity can be overcome by observing many galaxies which exhibit the same local shear, averaging down the noise by $\sigma = \sigma_\epsilon / \sqrt{N}$. In practice, telescopic views of the sky also need account for the blur of the atmosphere and optics and the cameras influence on the measurement, which can induce large biases. These biases must be calibrated away to the best of our ability using software after the measurement is made, and some attempts are made in Chapter 3.

In real observations, spurious correlations of observed galaxy shapes can also arise through incorrectly modeled distortions of the point spread function (PSF). One such PSF distortion comes from the propagation of light through correlated atmospheric patterns, leading to star/galaxy shape correlations depending on the weather and exposure time. Even space-based observations must deal with the tyranny of imperfect optics and systematics induced by the detector itself. All observations must use stars as a reference for the spurious PSF, used to either deconvolve or forward model galaxy images and measurements which are unbiased by observational conditions. In the next section we introduce how galaxy imaging surveys can be used to map overdensities of mass by leveraging the shear patterns they induce.

1.3 Cosmology from billions of pixels

Each photon collected in a CCD records a 2D position on the sky as well as its color from the selective transmission of the optics and absorption of the detector. However, on its billion-year-or-so journey, the path of the light ray is beset on all sides by the inequities of space-time which distort their otherwise straight paths. According to General Relativity, gravity's effect on this space-time can be described as a geometric curvature which is proportional to mass. Photons experience this distortion as they seek the shortest route, bending their apparent paths around massive objects similar to the way rays are bent in ordinary lenses. Depending on the path of the photon, gravitational lensing can weakly or strongly distort the image of a distant object in a measurable way. For instance, light from distant stars is deflected when passing nearby our Sun; when optically imaged during an eclipse, these stars at the solar limb are displaced from their

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actual positions by ~ 1.75 arcseconds (Dyson et al., 1920). Acute distortion of light rays passing nearest to the center of mass concentrations can also be seen in deep space images of clusters of galaxies. However, greater statistical power comes from the more numerous light rays that are only slightly distorted. For instance, sources of light up to 90° from the Sun are deflected by a few milliarcseconds, thousands of times less (but easily measured at radio wavelengths (Robertson et al., 1991)). Thus the phenomena of gravitational lensing broadly enables measurement of any general distribution of mass, given a distant enough source of light.

Distant galaxies provide one such source, and the measurement the slight distortions in their observed shapes is the province of so-called weak lensing. Weak lensing has become an essential tool for astrophysics and cosmology, as it provides observers with a tool to map and study the large scale mass structure. In the case of a single lensing mass, such as a cluster of galaxies in the foreground, the weak deflection of light causes images of background galaxies to appear tangentially aligned and stretched, as first detected in deep CCD images (Tyson et al., 1990). Conversely, an under-dense region of space cause images of distant galaxies to appear radially aligned to the center of the void (Melchior et al., 2014). Using source galaxies and lenses over a large volume, weak lens 3-dimensional cartography can map these mass distributions at different redshifts and enables measurement of the process of structure formation throughout the history in our Universe in the technique of cosmic shear (Bacon et al. (2000), Kaiser et al. (2000), Van Waerbeke et al. (2000), Wittman et al. (2000), and its tomographic evolution Jee et al. (2016)).

Unfortunately this cosmic shear signal is weak and individual galaxies have non-zero intrinsic ellipticities. Therefore many background galaxies need to be averaged to obtain a high signal-to-noise (S/N) measurement of the shear. For this reason, deep surveys of the sky have been specially designed to maximize the observed number density of background galaxies, decreasing the statistical uncertainty in the measured shear field by the square root of the observed number density of objects. Hence the power of modern weak lensing surveys then depends on the size of the cosmological volume it can probe. Notably, the LSST will have a 5σ depth of $r \sim 27$ (effectively hours of observing time on a 6.7 meter equivalent) across 18,000 square degrees at the end of its nominal 10 year survey, achieving depth by mosaicking and stacking exposures hundreds of exposures of each star and galaxy using a wide field of view and a massive camera. See Table 1.1 for examples of completed and ongoing surveys.

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These surveys aim to measure the weak lensing shear which in general relativity is related to the bending angle of photons determined by second derivatives of the lensing potential ψ : $\gamma_{ab}(\mathbf{x}) = (\partial_a \partial_b - \frac{1}{2} \delta_{ab} \nabla^2) \psi(\mathbf{x})$, also known as the tidal field. Using this knowledge, finite field, non-linear reconstruction techniques can be used to generate the locations and strengths of lensing potentials on the sky (Bartelmann (1995), Kilbinger (2015)), given deep enough observations of the shear. It was shown in Kaiser (1992) and Stebbins (1996) that the vector field representing the shear can be decomposed into two components in analogy with electromagnetism; namely, the electric component (so-called E, or gradient, non-vortical, or scalar perturbations) and magnetic component (so-called B, curl, vortical, or pseudo-scalar perturbations) of the shear field. These are illustrated in Figure 1.3.1. Hilbert et al. (2009) argue that to a good approximation lensing produces only E-modes, with B-modes thus an indication of systematic error. Accordingly, foreground density inhomogeneities are the primary source of observable E-mode patterns, while B-modes have been observed to have a much reduced amplitude, variously consistent with zero. Because of the undeniable usefulness of this decomposition relating E-modes to density perturbations, B-modes have been treated as a contaminant. The B-modes are often therefore not used, or are used as a test on of systematic error in the analysis rather than an astrophysical signal. For instance, it was shown in Guzik & Bernstein (2005) that spatially varying calibration errors in excess of 3% r.m.s. would generate B-modes larger than statistical errors.

However, there are good reasons to investigate B-modes outside of systematics tests. For instance, it was shown by Schneider et al. (2002) that an inhomogeneous (clustered) distribution of source galaxies can lead to an apparent B-mode. Additionally, if the orientation of background galaxies is non-random (statistical homogeneity and isotropy violation), a B-mode could be present depending on the scale of the intrinsic ellipticity of source galaxies.

One example of an anisotropy of source galaxy ellipticity comes from the intrinsic alignment of galaxies expected from direct tidal gravitational interactions of nearby structure, as first detected in Pen et al. (2000). Analytical calculations and simulations of these interactions is complicated however, and predictions of its strength, range, and orientation vary widely (Joachimi et al., 2013). There also exists a potentially interesting case for generating B-mode if two (or more) lensing clusters are projected along the line of sight. This so-called double lensing effect is shown in the maps of Bertin & Lombardi (2001) and the correlation functions of Cooray & Hu (2002). Finally,

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Figure 1.3.1: E and B-mode patterns. Positive E-modes patterns in the orientation of galaxies are directly generated when background galaxies are sheared tangentially by foreground overdensity. Positive and negative B-mode patterns can be generated through systematic error or indirectly through multiple lens/source configurations.

there is the possibility of tensor and vector perturbations contributing to both the E- and B-mode (Stebbins, 1996), as well as B-modes from the coupling of the E-mode and the Weyl tensor (Pitrou et al., 2015) induced by late-time anisotropy. Given the abundance of possible astrophysical sources of B-modes, it is worthwhile to conduct a comprehensive search for them (Bradshaw et al., 2017).

In this thesis we investigate B-modes in survey data as well as in simulations, treating them as a potentially useful signal instead of purely an indicator of systematic error. Both E- and B-modes are probed in 3-dimensional weak lensing via observational data as well as simulations of the successive lensing of background galaxies by foreground structure. The process of investigation begins from image data and proceeds through photometric redshift sample selection, shear estimation, aperture mass measurement, and analysis. We then reconstruct the observed lensing peaks in the field by estimating their mass and redshift and placing equivalent clusters in the simulation. Using the maps of the E-mode signal, made by filtering the tangential shear of galaxies around every point, we locate high S/N extended regions and associate them with a mass and redshift using the filtered tangential shear and the redshift clustering of galaxies along the line of light. In this way we can match the observed shear to a sum of successive lensing potentials and therefore can attribute any observed E- and B-modes as generated by gravitational lensing.

Chapter 2

The CCD and its Distortions

Astronomers use CCDs first as a transducer between light and electrons, and second as a way of precisely measuring the charge collected in the pixel regions which form an image. The silicon substrate acts as the former, and potential wells arranged by variable voltages define and enable the latter. But the array of silicon pixels which make up electronic images are not perfect, and may not faithfully represent the light as distributed on the sky. The distribution of light from a single galaxy or star, for instance, is subtly biased by the process of collection, transfer, and measurement which composes a single exposure. These subtle biases can become important when billions of galaxies are each imaged hundreds of times, as in the case of the surveys described in Section 1.1 and Table 1.1. Therefore, dedicated in-depth testing of the operation of CCDs is a necessary step to achieving the goals of modern CCD surveys of the sky.

Images begin to develop when incoming light generates photoelectrons in the silicon bulk, with a probabilistic absorption exponentially deeper for longer wavelengths of light. The details of absorption by the detector are discussed in Section 2.1, with examples of detector efficiency for several devices. Once excited to the conduction band, these photo-electrons are swept into potential wells which are defined by the voltages of a grid of implants and electrodes in the process of charge collection. However, transverse electric fields induced by nonuniformities in the chemical potential of the silicon and the collected charge itself can cause electrons to be diverted from purely parallel paths. This electron redistribution breaks the fundamental assumption of parallel charge transport and will be investigated in depth in Section 2.2. After an exposure ends, charge is then peristaltically clocked out of the array in the process of charge transfer discussed in Section 2.3. Finally, after

2.1. Charge generation

transfer to nearby amplifiers, the charge collected in each pixel is measured and converted from voltages to digitized measurement as described in Section 2.4. The entire process of imaging is thus broken into steps of charge generation, storage, transfer, and measurement, each of which can be measured, calibrated, and simulated. Each step of this signal chain has its own impact on the precision and accuracy of the resulting image analysis, and achieving more precise and accurate science requires deeper understanding of them all. In the following sections we will investigate this signal chain in CCDs using controlled lab experiments as well as detailed simulations of charge transport.

2.1 Charge generation

Images can be formed only after photons are first converted into electrons in the bulk silicon of a CCD. Modern CCD cameras are designed to convert as many incident photons into measurable electrons as possible, expressed as the quantum efficiency (QE) of the detector:

$$QE = \frac{N_e^-}{N_\gamma}. \quad (2.1.1)$$

and is on the order of a few percent for film, while for CCDs it can be as high as 80 to 90% as seen in Figure 2.1.1. QE is measured in practice using calibrated laboratory measurements involving calibrated picoammeter-sensitive photodiodes and scanning monochromators. The monochromator is first calibrated using a xenon lamp with known spectral lines to provide a basis for the wavelength of the scan to sub-micron accuracy. Then, the calibrated PD is placed inside the dewar at the location of the CCD and another PD is placed near the light source. The current as a function of wavelength is measured in both photodiodes, providing the calibration of the light source to flux N_γ (given known aperture sizes). Finally, the CCD is placed inside the dewar and the number of electrons N_e^- in an image at each wavelength is measured. This provides the QE as the ratio of measured electrons N_e^- to incident photons N_γ at a given wavelength. Plotted in Figure 2.1.1 is the mean QE of two different LSST prototype sensors and the mean of the ten CCDs comprising the Suprime-cam (Miyazaki et al., 2002). Variations in the QE at short wavelengths $\lambda < 800nm$ are mainly due to differences in anti-reflection coatings.

2.1. Charge generation

Several physical processes can result in generation of charge within the CCD, however the most dominant source of electrons, given a band-limited source of light, is the photoelectric effect. Photoelectricity was originally discovered in metals when incident light caused photo-ejection of electrons from the surface, sometimes even forming arcs under intense sources of light. This effect is tamed in the silicon bulk of a CCD, where photo-ejection is replaced with a subtler photo-excitation of an electron from the valence band to the conduction band. For most modern CCDs used in optical astronomy, a slab of p-type silicon serves as the substrate where this photoconversion occurs. This substrate is highly resistive, and high voltages can be applied to deplete it of mobile holes to better than one part in 10^{11} (von Ammon & Herzer, 1984).

Once a photon enters the silicon, often aided by surface anti-reflection coatings, it can excite an electron into conduction if it exceeds the so-called band gap, E_{gap} . In a semiconductor such as silicon, $E_{gap} = 1.1eV$ which corresponds to a minimum wavelength of $1100nm$ for photons to be directly photoconverted, (though indirect conversion with help from e.g. phonons or impurities is possible). This band gap therefore imparts an abrupt cut-off to the $QE(\lambda)$ of CCDs. However, photons with enough energy to bridge the band gap are still limited by the probability of interaction with the Si bulk. The probability of interaction can be represented as an absorption length, shown as the black line in Figure 2.1.1. The absorption length corresponds to the distance after which the light has fallen to $1/e$ of the original flux or where about 36% of light is unconverted. For instance, given a CCD silicon thickness of 40 and 100 μm , this corresponds to $\sim 64\%$ absorption at wavelengths ~ 920 and 975 nanometers. Gaining an extra 50 nanometers of near infrared sensitivity is a valuable achievement, especially given the desire to survey higher redshifts. For this reason, modern CCDs are often designed with thicker silicon substrates to allow these longer wavelengths more room to photoconvert. However, this achievement does come at a cost. The additional thickness of silicon leads to longer charge transport times, allowing their paths to become more affected by transverse electric fields described in the next section.

Also plotted in Figure 2.1.1 is the average QE of ten CCDs fabricated by MIT-LL which provided the focal plane array for the Suprime-cam imager used for the weak lensing reduction and analysis in Sections 3.3 and 4.1.1.

2.1. Charge generation

Figure 2.1.1: The efficiency of light absorption of CCDs as a function of wavelength. On the left vertical axis, quantum efficiency ranges from 0 to 1, and the red, green, and blue curves are different CCDs plotted with respect to QE. Two $100\mu\text{m}$ thick LSST CCD chips (v1 and v2 shown in blue and green) have their QE measured as in Section 2.1. Their measurable difference in efficiency is mainly in the anti-reflection coatings which dominate short wavelength charge generation performance. An example QE curve for the thinner ($40\mu\text{m}$) and less efficient MIT-LL fabricated CCDs used in the Suprime-cam are also shown in red. On the right vertical axis the absorption length in silicon is shown, and the thickness of both LSST CCD silicon wafers and MIT chips are indicated. Absorption length dominates CCD charge generation efficiency at longer wavelengths, and therefore CCDs for modern deep astronomical surveys are thicker by design.

2.2. Charge transport

Figure 2.2.1: Mobile charge distribution in LSST CCD simulation. Channel stops formed by ion implants are shown in yellow, which collect holes shown in red and define fixed columns of the CCD. The electrons, shown in blue, are collected in the potential well of the central pixel in a narrow depth near the gate structure shown in green, which have variable voltages enabling clocking.

2.2 Charge transport

If left to themselves the liberated electrons would readily recombine with the holes they left in the valence band. For a measurement to be made, the generated charges must therefore be separated and moved to collection at a site which corresponds to a minimum of potential energy. In CCDs, this separation is provided by a negative bias voltage applied to the surface of the silicon, on the order of tens of volts. This negative bias sweeps photo-electrons toward collection in a grid of pixels with rows and columns defined by a lattice of capacitive gates and channel stops. The fabrication of these gates and channels has gone through many iterations over the decades, and modern techniques are worthy of a brief description to fully understand pixel geometry. The channel stops which define the edges of columns in the pixel grid are n-type semiconducting regions which induce a negative potential boundary for electrons. During fabrication, these n-type regions are defined first through photolithographic processes of masking and ion implantation of phosphorus to

2.2. Charge transport

form the stops. The unmasked region above the channel stop implant is then thermally oxidized. This creates an insulating structure on top of the implanted region, where oxidation into the surface of the silicon physically and electrically separates pixel columns. The interior of the pixel columns, where electrons collect, is then implanted with p-type elements such as boron after etching of the remaining mask away. Further oxidation covers this entire surface, allowing the charge collection area to be isolated from surface traps in so-called buried channel devices, now universally used. Finally, a poly-silicon gate structure is then added on top of these columns, so that charge can be localized by the parallel clock voltages applied during collection. The final electro-chemical configuration of a pixel is illustrated in Figure 2.2.1. An X-Y slice through the bottom 1/100th of the pixel is shown in the top left, illustrating the separation of electrons and holes (blue and red) during collection. Slices in the X-Z and Y-Z direction are shown on the bottom and right sides, respectively, again showing the localization of collected charge as well as the gate/oxide pattern in green/yellow.

The deep pixel depth of the LSST sensors that enabled the detection of redder photons in the previous section implies longer electron transport times. This allows more time for a photoelectron to be acted upon by transverse electric fields sourced by impurity gradients (tree rings), collected charge (brighter-wider), or outside potentials (edge effects) which we can measure in the lab and compare to simulations. We individually investigate each of these effects in simulations by setting up Poisson's equation with realistic approximations to the potential well shape from boundary voltages and charges. Examples of these simulation setups for an array of 3x3 pixels is shown in Figure 2.2.1, and the edge of CCDs in Figure 2.2.4. Charge collection can then be simulated by sequentially injecting photo electrons from a given source distribution (taken to be a Gaussian profile) into the simulated potentials.

2.2.1 Tree rings

Astrometric distortions which are fixed (static) in their CCD location are particularly troublesome because of the pattern they imprint on every exposure. One such astrometric distortion comes from the fixed-pattern of so-called tree rings seen in silicon wafers used as the substrate for CCDs. These tree rings are formed during fabrication through the crystal growth process through dopant impurities in the molten silicon. As the molten silicon is sequentially radially layered on the crystal,

2.2. Charge transport

Figure 2.2.2: Tree rings as observed in flat field images (top) and in the astrometric distortion (bottom). Units of flat field variations are expressed as percentages ranging from -1 to 1, and astrometric errors are presented in units of pixels. Sub-percent variations in the flux each pixel collects are induced by tiny dopant variations in the silicon bulk. The astrometric error is calculated by differencing the expected and measured positions of thousands of spots which have been dithered across the frame. Each image of the spots has been flat-fielded, indicating the astrometric error is still present in the flattened data.

2.2. Charge transport

these dopant variations result in a fixed pattern of varying resistivity which affects charge transport. This leaves a detectable pattern in flat fields and also induces an astrometric error which we can characterize. Figure 2.2.2 illustrates the pattern of tree rings in a flat field (top) at the sub-percent level, and the astrometric error induced (bottom). We measure the astrometric error in the region of these tree rings by dithering thousands of spots across the CCD and calculating the displacement of spot centroids from their expected positions.

It has been historically assumed that the tree rings only induce effective QE variations and can be flat-fielded out of the data. However, the astrometric error measured in these studies has been flat-fielded, indicating the effect on astrometry is not compensated during the flat-fielding process. This therefore raises the question of whether flat-fielding is safe for modern astronomical surveys (Baumer et al., 2017), a technique which has always been a part of basic image processing. Each survey must answer this question individually, by taking into account the precision they aim to achieve and the characteristics of each detector. Thankfully, the tree rings have recently been greatly reduced through precise control of thermal and temporal variations during fabrication, and LSST CCDs have rings with ~ 50 times less amplitude relative to other modern surveys with thick silicon substrates as noted in Okura et al. (2016). At this level, it was shown that tree rings present in LSST CCDs should have negligible impact on the shear power spectrum and cosmological parameter estimation.

2.2.2 Brighter and wider PSFs

Astrometric distortions can also be induced by the dynamic distribution of electrons already collected in the potential well. This dynamic effect has been seen in CCDs for decades but only recently came under scrutiny in the era of precision cosmology (Antilogus et al., 2014). Precise measurement of its effect can be observed in surveys of stellar fields with many PSFs. Using the beam simulator in the UC Davis laboratory, we can test some of the analysis methods on real data. In particular, we can simulate the analysis of star-like objects which have realistic PSF profiles by imaging an array of pinholes placed in front of the light source. These spot arrays can be variously designed, but we use circular apertures 3 or $30\mu m$ in diameter which reproduce either sub-pixel sized PSFs or those on the order of the expected PSF size for the LSST ~ 0.6 arcsecond seeing sampled by 0.2 arcsecond pixels.

2.2. Charge transport

Figure 2.2.3: The bias in the size of PSFs as a function of brightness modeled with pixelized Gaussians. This brighter-wider effect systematically biases the critical step of PSF estimation in CCD exposures used for weak lensing analysis. The blue and green points show the growth in the size of spots in the x and y directions as a function of brightness. Red dashed lines show the slope of Poisson-simulated spots measured through the same forward modeling process of fitting.

In Figure 2.2.3 we investigate the brighter-wider effect as measured through forward model fitting of both pixelized Gaussian images in the lab and from the Poisson simulator. In these tests thousands of spots are simultaneously fit, as a single spot does not have enough information to characterize the brightness dependence (which is on the order of a percent). First, spots are identified using the image segmentation algorithm in **SExtractor**, which identifies thousands of pixel peaks in the images. Then each image is then cut into small postage stamps of 9×9 and spots in a chosen region are forward modeled with pixelized elliptical Gaussians. The $\sigma_{x,y}$ which best fits all the postage stamps in each exposure is found by minimization of the difference between measured and simulated profiles. The same forward modeling fitting process is used on the Poisson-simulated images, which are built up through realistic charge transport of electrons. The slope of the Poisson simulation is shown as the dashed line, which closely matches the observed slope in the data.

2.2.3 Distorted edge pixels

Electric fields sourced by the readout electronics can similarly divert photoelectrons. As an example, the so-called scupper is a feature implemented around the edges of the CCD package to protect

2.2. Charge transport

Figure 2.2.4: Optical microscopic view of the edge of the CCD, compared to setup in Poisson.

the signal in the imaging array from any charges generated on the periphery. This ring is on the top edge of the field of the view in Figure 2.2.4, and is usually set at a high positive potential which can be felt by photoelectrons in the bulk. Other readout electronics on the edges of each CCD can divert the photoelectron, and inclusion of each realistic detail has shown improvement in the matching to observation. In fact, many different observational conditions have been tested, varying CCD voltages and collections schemes as well as in different filters, summarized in Figure 2.2.5. Four different experiments are shown in that figure, which vary: 1) back bias voltage, 2) filter of observation (and thus photoconversion depth), 3) scupper voltage, and 4) the charge collection scheme.

To measure the astrometric error in each of these schemes, thousands of pinholes are dithered approaching the CCD edge and the displacement of spot centroids from their expected positions is calculated. In each case, the diversion of photoelectrons toward the external electronics is seen of varying amplitude, peaking at ~ 2 pixels in from the edge. The astrometric error then quickly

2.2. Charge transport

goes negative (retrograde) to the edge due to the ordinary occultation of the spot (Bradshaw et al., 2015). In simulations, the photoelectron drift is captured by the solving of Poisson's equations. The distorted pixel boundaries which result from the edge potentials are then used to pixelize a Gaussian profile, and the astrometric shift is measured similarly as the difference between input centroid and that which is measured (including the occultation effect by design). The simulations, though not perfect matches to the data, are successful in capturing the general onset, shape, and amplitude of the astrometric error observed in the CCDs under varying conditions. This indicates that the same simulations (and input CCD design specifications) used in the measurement of the brighter-wider effect can be generalized to modeling the edges of CCDs as well.

The back bias voltage has the largest effect on the astrometric error at the edge. Operation of LSST CCDs uses nominal potential of -60V, which draws photoelectrons to the pixel array the fastest. Lesser potentials (-40,-20 V) provide more time for photoelectrons to drift toward the edges of the array. Strangely, it is observed in the laboratory that a zero back side bias still results in successful charge transport, though with unacceptable systematic errors. Simulations of charge transport calculations with no back side bias do not converge, however, indicating some potentials in the bulk are yet unaccounted for.

Varying filters of observation also has an effect on the astrometric error, with larger astrometric error seen in bluer filters (though the bluest filter we use is still the R band). This is due to the longer transport times for photoelectrons generated higher in the bulk by bluer photons. The reddest filter, y_2 , has the least astrometric error. Observations in the V or B bands whose photoelectrons entirely convert at surface of the CCD will most likely have slightly higher astrometric errors, though not by much as the R band photons already photoconvert only a few microns into the bulk.

A good portion of the astrometric error at the edge is induced by the scupper voltage, usually set to ~ 20 volts. Making the potential more positive increases the attractive force felt by the negative photoelectrons during their transport to the pixel well. Therefore, varying this potential slightly by raising it by ± 5 volts has a measurable effect in the observations and simulations.

Finally, the parallel clocks which trap collected photoelectrons in their pixel wells can also have an effect on charge transport. Having two phases high during collection, shown in the clock cycle drawing in Figure 1.1.1 and which is the nominal operational condition for the LSST, slightly increases the average potential felt by photoelectrons during transport. Having only one phase high

2.3. Charge transfer

Figure 2.2.5: Summary of the astrometric error at the edge as measured in the laboratory and simulated via Poisson's equations.

results in a less positive average potential in the bulk, implying longer charge transport times and more time to be affected by transverse edge potentials. This effect is measurable in the data and was also captured by the Poisson simulations.

2.3 Charge transfer

For a CCD detector with low readout noise in mind, the charge measurement must be performed by low-noise readout amplifiers. Practical constraints dictate that the miniaturization of these low-noise readout amplifiers must be on the order of ten times the pixel size. Therefore to maintain critical sampling of the PSF and low noise, each pixel have its charge amplified elsewhere, necessitating charge transfer.

The process of transfer begins after an exposure ends and the shutter is closed, when the parallel clock starts cycling each row of pixels down by one. The entire cycle of parallel clocks is shown schematically on the right of Figure 1.1.1, illustrating the trapping of electrons under positive voltage gates. The first parallel transfer places the first row of charge into the serial register (shown

2.3. Charge transfer

Figure 2.3.1: Parallel clocking the LSST CCD

as the purple region in Figure 1.1.1). Before the next cycle of the parallel clock, the entire serial register must be clocked out to the readout amplifier. The serial clocks are therefore running at a tremendous rate, while the parallel clocks can run slower by a factor of the number of serial transfers. However, the charge transfer process can be segmented by having multiple readout amplifiers on each CCD; for instance, a 4k by 4k pixel array can be broken into 16 segments of 500 columns by 2000 rows. In our lab setting we follow LSST-like constraints which dictate a readout of two seconds. Therefore, the CCD readout must measure half a million pixels each second, implying the serial and parallel clocks run at 500 and 1 kHz respectively.

2.3.1 Clocking out the charge

As described in the previous section, charge packets are stored in the collecting phases, P1 and P2, between two parallel barrier phases defined by P3. To begin the transfer, the parallel barrier furthest from the serial readout, P2, is switched to a barrier phase, isolating electrons in P1. Next, P3 is switched to a collecting phase, allowing the electrons to move into this region of higher potential. The charge proceeds to fill the two collecting phases, equally dividing via electrostatic repulsion. P1 then becomes a barrier phase in addition to P2, fully shifting the charge to the P3 region only. In this way, charge which was collected in high potential regions under P1 and P2 are now collected under P3. By turning P2 to a collecting phase, and then P3 to a barrier phase, the

2.4. Measurement of charge: gain and noise

charge has been fully transported down by one pixel. These parallel phases repeat until all of the charge has been clocked into the serial register. Their voltages and timings are shown in a screen capture of readout in Figure 2.3.1.

2.3.2 Charge transfer inefficiency

Charge transfer efficiency (CTE) measures the ability of the CCD to transfer charge from one pixel to the next. The fraction of charge left behind from a single transfer defines the inefficiency of charge transfer, $CTI=1-CTE$, and is can be measured via several techniques. One of the techniques is the extended pixel edge response or EPER technique. This technique measures CTE using a flat field exposure and measuring the amount of charge found in the overscan region. Charge located in this region is either from noise or from deferred charge leftover during transfer. To rid the measurement of noise, many lines can be averaged together, which has been done in the figure. This allows a measurement of the deferred charge, Q_d , in comparison to that of the last column, Q_{LC} .

$$CTE_{EPER} = 1 - \frac{Q_{deferred}}{N_{serial} * Q_{LC}} \quad (2.3.1)$$

where N_{serial} is the number of transfers over which the deferred charge could have accumulated. For LSST CCDs the maximum allowable CTE for device acceptance is very stringent, greater than .999995. The measurements of EPER on this prototype device indicate a CTE of .999675, with performance varying among devices. The variations in CTE between devices warrants investigation, as large transfer losses can bias shape measurement.

2.4 Measurement of charge: gain and noise

The pixel analog-to-digital unit (ADU) values which make up an image are finally recorded at the end of the signal chain in the analog-to-digital converter (ADC). Each ADU value is related to the number of electrons in each pixel through the gain of the system g , which is the product of all the voltage amplifications which occur in the signal chain. The electrons in each pixel are first amplified when they are dumped on to the output node, often resulting in a few μV per electron. This voltage level is compared to a reference level which is measured to the precision allowable by the ADC in a process known as correlated double sampling, essentially removing low f noise. The

2.4. Measurement of charge: gain and noise

Figure 2.4.1: Photon transfer method of determining system gain, $g = e^-/ADU$. Top: A series of exposures with increasing exposure levels used to measure the gain of the CCD. The broadening of the histogram of pixel values is due to Poisson noise which is directly related to the illumination level. Showing the variance vs. signal in ADU (bias subtracted) for 16 amplifiers in an LSST CCD. Groups of amplifiers which are read out to shared preamp boards are shown as similar colors indicating variation in off-chip electronic gain. The linear relationship is due to Poisson counting statistics.

final digitization is usually done using 16 bits ($ADU_{max} = 65535$) with a variable reference bias level to prevent negative values which would need an extra bit to represent.

However, physical units are often needed to calibrate the detector and so this process of conversion must be reversed. At zero illumination and with the shutter closed, there is only read noise on top of a bias level. This bias level must be subtracted from all images first to provide the illumination level in ADU. At non-zero illumination levels, there is a spread in the distribution of pixel values which is larger for increasing exposure levels, as seen in the histograms of pixel values at the top of Figure 2.4.1. This variance comes from the Poisson statistics of counting photons which increases linearly with the photon count $\sigma_{ADU}^2 = gS_{ADU}$. The gain of a CCD can be measured in practice by taking a series of flat field images at increasing illumination levels. One such series of exposures is shown in the top panel of Figure 2.4.1, and the variance increase is shown in the

2.4. Measurement of charge: gain and noise

bottom of the figure. By measuring the variance of each exposure, carefully avoiding contaminated pixel regions, the increase in Poisson noise can be measured and compared to the signal level. The conversion between signal ADU and electrons, the device gain, is thus directly obtained from flat field exposures by the slope of the line in the variance vs. signal level plane.

Chapter 3

Photometry and Shape Measurement on Distorted and Pixelized Images

Images of the sky using pixel detectors provide the astronomer with a uniform grid of brightness measurements. These brightness measurements are convoluted by the pixelization process, which essentially integrates of the object’s intrinsic surface brightness morphology over each pixel’s collecting area. This summation within a pixel naturally leads to more flux in a pixel than would be produced by sampling surface brightness with delta-function like pixels, leading to wider observed object profiles. Some algorithms, for example the method of second moments presented in Section 1.2, assumes well sampled and non-pixelized images in order to accurately relate the calculated moments $M_{2,0}, M_{0,2}, M_{11}$ to the intrinsic object width parameters $\sigma_x\sigma_y$ and orientation ϕ . With very well sampled images this pixelization affects the PSF in a minor way, and thus the locations and shapes of detected objects are not greatly affected. However, as the size of an object approaches the pixel scale, this pixel binning and discrete sampling can create a small but measurable systematic bias in the calculation of some parameters.

In general, every measurement of size is biased at some level, and the relationship of image size measurement to gravitational lensing is one of necessary calibration (Mandelbaum et al., 2015). For surveys which rely upon precise and accurate parameter estimation of hundreds of billions of pixelized images of faint stars and galaxies, these algorithmic biases are necessary to understand. Several modern surveys provide public shear catalogs: CFHTLenS, KiDS, DLS, DES, and HSC

3.1. The size and orientation of pixelized Gaussians

(Miller et al. (2013),Jee et al. (2016),Jarvis et al. (2016), Mandelbaum et al. (2017)). Together they provide a sampling of different shear measurement techniques on various detectors and telescopes, revealing varying systematic effects of pixelization. The problem of size bias in the case of 1D Gaussians is illustrated in the next section; then, the effect of this size bias on measurements of orientation angle of 2D Gaussians is described.

3.1 The size and orientation of pixelized Gaussians

To illustrate the systematic bias in the method of moments it is easiest to begin with a one dimensional Gaussian profile centered at zero: $I_G(x) = \exp(-x^2/\sigma^2)$. Pixelized profiles I_{pix} are calculated by integrating the Gaussian profile along the x direction in steps of chosen pixel size δ_x , resulting in differences of scaled error functions:

$$I_{pix}(x_i) = \int_{x_i - \delta_x/2}^{x_i + \delta_x/2} I_G(x) dx = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sigma \left(\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x_c - (x_i - \delta_x/2)}{\sqrt{2}\sigma}\right) - \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x_c + (x_i - \delta_x/2)}{\sqrt{2}\sigma}\right) \right). \quad (3.1.1)$$

This naturally leads to pixel values which are higher than the value of the Gaussian I_G sampled at points along the pixel center, which effectively broadens the image. For smaller input σ widths this broadening is proportionally larger, leading to a bias which is dependent upon the size of the profile in relation to the pixel scale. The pixelization process can be undone if the σ of the input profile is known, but in practice one must measure σ from the data, requiring iteration and/or feedback. Additionally, real galaxy images are not Gaussian profiles and usually exhibit sharper cores and broader wings. More realistic profiles such as Sersic or disc/bulge models can instead be fit to pixelized images, but ultimately suffer from similar biases. This section illustrates the problem of bias in even the most simple and optimal of circumstances. In the following subsections we explore this bias in simulations and show how it induces angular preferences in the estimation of galaxy orientation.

3.1.1 Second moments

The biased second moments on 1 dimensional Gaussian summarizes the loss of information from pixelization, where both both the regular sampling and the averaging of flux within a pixel well

3.1. The size and orientation of pixelized Gaussians

Figure 3.1.1: The bias in the measurement of second moments on a pixelized 1 dimensional Gaussian. The blue line shows the rapid decrease in second moment error for a Gaussian which is sampled at discrete points and not integrated over pixel areas (as in the CCD), shown as the green line. The red line shows the second moment error when calculated upon an image which has a first-order correction to its profile based upon an estimate of the σ itself. Any bias in size measurement which is a function of the size itself leads to an orientation bias discussed in Subsection 3.1.2.

lead to information loss and bias. These two effects can be seen in Figure 3.1.1 as the blue and green lines, which shows the percentage systematic error on the measured moments compared to input ones. Correcting the pixelized profile with an approximation to the difference between the filled and point-like pixels before calculating the second moment leads to a reduced error on σ by an order of magnitude or more, as shown by the red line. Although all of these effects fall off rapidly as resolution (σ relative to pixel scale) increases, all are still biased especially at small σ . The difficult part about this size bias is that it is dependent upon the size itself, so any correction in the algorithm must necessarily take in an estimate of the size. In fact it is the bias's dependence on size that leads to an interesting effect seen in galaxy survey catalogs of shapes.

3.1. The size and orientation of pixelized Gaussians

3.1.2 Orientation bias

In two dimensional images the pixelization process is compounded and the biased broadening of pixelized profiles presents a new problem. Imagine first that an elliptical Gaussian profile has its major axis oriented along the x axis. The measured second moment along that direction, M_{20} , slightly overestimates the actual σ_x in that direction as discussed in the previous section. Similarly, the y -moment M_{02} is an overestimate of σ_y by some larger amount due to the smaller spatial extent of the minor axis relative to the pixel grid. The moment along the x-y direction (the covariance) is also overestimated by varying amounts depending upon the axis ratio of the objects and their sizes relative to the pixel grid. Now rotate the same fixed-size Gaussian by a some small (known) angle $< 45^\circ$ and perform the pixelization and second moment calculations as before. The biased estimates M_{20}, M_{02} of sizes σ_x and σ_y are now different because the Gaussian profile relative to the pixel axes has changed. In the y direction, M_{02} is biased less as the major axis of the Gaussian is directed along its axis, and conversely in the x direction M_{20} is biased more because the major axis is no longer aligned, presenting an effectively smaller Gaussian to the x pixel axis. Orient the Gaussian profile along a 45° angle and the bias in x and y moments are equal.

These varying levels of systematic error as a function of angle and axis ratio (ellipticity) are clearly troublesome, and they hint at a fundamental flaw in the estimation of orientation as a ratio of biased sizes. If there is any bias in estimating an object's size (and at some level there must be), then that size bias can alternately push and pull estimates of size and bias the angles inferred from the sizes along the pixel axes. A size bias is thus converted into an orientation bias, with clear angular preference at multiples of 45° . However, the simple simulations show that other preferred angles show up near integer fractions of π when sources are both large and elliptical enough to have pixelization effect their profile. Therefore, this biased orientation angle is not purely an effect of small poorly sampled images. Figure 3.1.2 shows the angular bias in data from the Deep Lens Survey (DLS) compared to the second moment bias in simulated pixelized Gaussians. In that figure, the π -periodicity of angular preference is shown to be related intrinsic orientation of the object as well as its axis ratio r . Two example simulations of galaxies with axis ratios of 4-to-1 and 2-to-1 ($r = 0.25, 0.5$) are shown alongside the distribution of orientation angles from the DLS. In the simulations, a Gaussian with a fixed axis ratio is rotated by some angle θ_{in} and pixelized,

3.1. The size and orientation of pixelized Gaussians

Figure 3.1.2: The orientation bias of pixelized Gaussians. The two right flower-like plots show a polar plot of the systematic measurement error on the orientation angle for Gaussians with an minor to major axis ratio of 1 to 4 and 1 to 2 on the top and bottom, respectively. The more elliptical Gaussian has more bias and it changes more as a function of angle. These colorful figures illustrate the size (sigma, or width) dependence of the orientation bias effect. Shown on the left are the histograms of the orientation angle for all objects (blue) in one field of the Deep Lens Survey which are fitted with an elliptical Gaussian profile (see section 3.3.2 for a description of the measurement code). Also plotted in the top and bottom histograms are the slices of the data which have axis ratios ranging from $.2 < r < .3$ and $.4 < r < .6$, in green. In red, the size bias described in section 3.1.1 and Figure 3.1.1 is shown to induce an angular bias. These minima of absolute orientation angle error are perhaps picked up by the shape measurement code which does not directly use second moments.

3.1. The size and orientation of pixelized Gaussians

then second moments are used to estimate orientation angle θ_{out} . The difference, θ_{err} , between the input orientation and that measured from the (biased) second moments is recorded and shown to have varying sign in the flower-like plots on the right. Additionally, the radial direction in the flower plots shows the amplitude of θ_{err} dependence upon the size of the major axis. It can be seen that the pattern of bias is different between the two axis ratios, with more elliptical $r = 0.25$ galaxies experiencing more bias and toward more angles than $[-90, -45, 0, +45, +90]$. The effect on the histogram of orientation angles is shown on the left, where the red line shown is the absolute value of θ_{err} at that axis ratio, and the blue and green lines represent the entire DLS shape catalog $0 < r < 1$ in contrast to those with axis ratios selected to be close to the simulated one. The slices of axis ratio chosen and the entire distribution of axis ratios (ellipticities) of the entire sample are shown in the middle histogram.

It is seen that the sharpness and preference in angles shown in is related to the observed ellipticity distribution, which in turn is related to the seeing and PSF size relative to pixel scale. Therefore, one would expect that the particular fingerprint of orientation bias might vary from survey to survey. Orientation bias in other surveys is shown in Figure 3.1.3 showing many different patterns in the orientation angles, with varying peak to trough ratios and preferred orientations due to each survey's various seeing conditions, cameras, and shape measurement algorithm. One may worry that the angular preference comes from the diffraction around support vanes which hold the camera at prime focus, which creates spikes around bright stars. Each of the telescope/camera combinations in Figure 3.1.3 have four such support vanes, at varying angles to the instrument. However, surveys with the same telescope (e.g. DLS and DES) show different angular preference. Each survey also shows angular preference at more than 4 angles, with a pattern again dependent upon the intrinsic object's axis ratio. The least-biased survey's angles (HSC) is the most recent and most incomplete catalog, but perhaps indicates some success in self-calibrating the size bias away (Huff & Mandelbaum, 2017). As a whole, this collection of survey data indicate that the problem of determining a galaxy's orientation angle from biased size estimates is an unsolved problem.

3.1. The size and orientation of pixelized Gaussians

Figure 3.1.3: The bias in the measurement of orientation using various galaxy surveys and measurement algorithms. When available, recommended data cuts (exclusion of flagged objects, for instance) are applied. The ultimate shape of the orientation angle bias is dependent upon the distribution of object sizes relative to the camera’s pixel scale and the models which are fit to galaxies.

3.2 Laboratory object analysis

In our laboratory, the CCD and dewar are mounted on an xyz stage (and shown as element D in Figure 1.1.2) which allows for micron-precise 3D motion, enabling dithering and focusing. Additionally, the CCD dewar mount has pitch and yaw control via a mount screw and a rotating stage. These xyz motions can be used to align and focus the beam on the surface of the CCD by taking sequential exposures and analyzing images of the spot array. Near focus ($z \sim 0$) the width of the spot is directly proportional to its distance from the focal plane, increasing quadratically in $\pm z$ direction. Therefore the focal plane location for each xy position on the CCD can be approximately found by measuring the minimum of second moment as a function of stage position. By stepping through z positions around best focus, tip and tilt of the CCD can be corrected for by minimizing differences in the z location of minimum moment. This process results in alignment and focusing of the camera, which only needs adjustment when large changes are made to the system. The aligned and focused images can then be used to simulate observing, and the effects of charge transport (e.g. brighter-wider subsection 2.2.2) on the profile can be measured. Purposefully defocused images can also provide information about the optical distortions present and can be used to fit models of aberration in the lab.

3.2.1 Higher moments of spot images

For a simple Gaussian pixelized by point-like pixels, the first and second moments in the xy directions completely describe the shape of the Gaussian. However, for realistic pixels which sum light over their collecting area these moments are insufficient. What's more, realistic PSF profiles are not Gaussians, and in CCD observations their brightness also effects their observed profile as in Section 2.2. Higher moments, those with $i, j > 2$ as described in Equation 1.2.1 also contain information. We illustrate the dependence of moments in Figure 3.2.1, where the centroid, width, skewness, and kurtosis of spots in the lab are measured as a function of brightness. These results indicate that the brighter-wider effect in CCDs does not just affect the size but also have higher order effects on the profile.

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Figure 3.2.1: Measurement of the distortion moments measured on PSF images ($30\mu\text{m}$ pinhole) as a function of brightness. Thousands of spots were imaged and measured at increasing exposure levels to reveal the dependence of PSF shape on collected charges. The first moment, in the upper left, shows the subpixel centroid distribution of spots in the x (blue) and y (red) directions as a function of brightness. The broadening of the second moment, which was described with the Poisson model in subsection 2.2.2, is shown in the upper right. Saturation of pixel wells can be seen in that panel as the sharp increase in second moment at high electron counts. The third and fourth moments in the bottom left and right panels, which represent skewness and kurtosis, are also functions of brightness. In particular the kurtosis, which describes the profile's tails and shoulders and is equal to 3 for a perfect Gaussian, shows a clear trend similar to the second moments. These measurements indicate that the brighter-wider effect in CCDs is not simply a function of size. Error bars are computed from the dispersion of calculated moments in a given brightness bin, which have a large intrinsic spread due to pixelization.

3.2. Laboratory object analysis

Figure 3.2.2: Examples of aberrated intrafocal spots in the lab (left), compared with the model prediction made from extrafocal images (center). Residuals are shown with a $\pm 10\%$ scale from red to blue (right). Coefficients across the focal plane have been interpolated to produce an xy map, which can be used to predict images at different z .

3.2.2 Laboratory optical aberration modeling

Despite the advantages offered by bringing light to a clear focus, there is also useful information in the analysis purposefully defocused spots. These donut-like images of the pupil plane (with a central obscuration) spread each spot's light over a larger area and in a fashion which is familiar to optometrists. In particular, the defocused spots clearly reveal optical aberrations which can then be described with circular Zernike polynomials (Zernike, 1934). Each Zernike term has a particular form in both radial ρ and azimuthal θ directions as shown in Equations 3.2.1 and 3.2.3:

$$Z_n^m(\rho, \theta) = R_n^m(\rho) \cos(m\theta); \quad m \geq 0 \quad (3.2.1)$$

$$Z_n^{-m}(\rho, \theta) = R_n^m(\rho) \sin(m\theta); \quad m < 0 \quad (3.2.2)$$

where the radial form R_n^m can be expressed as a binomial product

$$R_n^m(\rho) = \sum_{k=0}^{\frac{n-m}{2}} (-1)^k \binom{n-k}{k} \binom{n-2k}{\frac{n-m}{2}-k} \rho^{n-2k}. \quad (3.2.3)$$

The first eleven polynomials are listed in Table 3.1, along with their corresponding aberrations. These terms are all orthogonal, and thus encapsulate images in non-redundant moments similar to those described in Section 3.2.1.

3.2. Laboratory object analysis

Figure 3.2.3: Modeling the optical distortions in the lab with Zernike aberration fitting to thousands of spots. Shown are the spatial patterns of 11 coefficients across the focal plane are measured (in units of waves at $700nm$). Once the aberrations are encapsulated they can be used to predict the PSF at all xyz locations.

The process of defocused observation to characterize aberration is known as curvature wavefront sensing (CWFS), and is used in the optical alignment of the Dark Energy Camera (Roodman et al., 2014) and the active optical system in the LSST will make use of intra and extra-focal (split) CCDs to help model the PSF (Xin et al., 2015). Calculation and modeling of these Zernike aberrations will thus be critical to accurate imaging of the sky (Schechter & Sobel Levinson, 2011), and we can use this knowledge to focus our camera as well. We can simulate the process of CWFS in the lab by analyzing the defocused spots as a function of z position. We model spot images with the Zernike formalism to third order plus spherical aberration, for a total of 11 different aberration coefficients: xy tilt, defocus and FWHM, xy astigmatism, xy coma, xy trefoil, and primary spherical. Aberrations observed in the lab can be seen on the left of Figure 3.2.2 where coma and astigmatism are especially apparent in the 64 sample images shown across the CCD. The model fitting proceeds through numerical minimization of the model/data difference by varying these 11 parameters on thousands of spots across the surface of the CCD. The best fit coefficients of each aberration can be smoothly interpolated to any xy point on the CCD, as shown in the 2D maps of the coefficients shown in Figure 3.2.3. Using the fitted parameters, models of the

3.3. Analysis of deep Subaru prime focus imaging

Table 3.1: Zernike polynomials and their associated aberrations

Aberration	n,m	radial form	azimuthal form
Piston (FWHM)	(0,0)	1	1
Tip,tilt	(1,1),(1,-1)	ρ	$\cos \theta, \sin \theta$
Defocus	(2,0)	ρ^2	1
Astigmatism x,y	(2,2),(2,-2)	ρ^2	$\sin 2\theta, \cos 2\theta$
Coma x,y	(3,1),(3,-1)	$3\rho^3 - 2\rho$	$\sin \theta, \cos \theta$
Trefoil x,y	(3,3),(3,-3)	ρ^3	$\sin 3\theta, \cos 3\theta$
Spherical	4,0	$6\rho^4 - 6\rho^2 + 1$	1

aberrations can be subtracted from the observed spot profiles, as shown in the middle and right panels of Figure 3.2.2. In addition, the Zernike focus parameter can be varied to provide optical aberrations at different z values, and can predict intrafocal images from extrafocal ones, or in the case of CWFS for sky surveys, the PSFs of objects in focus. We therefore successfully demonstrate this technique using semi-realistic star-like objects which will be found on the split CCDs at the edge of the LSST focal plane. Use of this extra/intra-focal imagery will be critical to the success of the LSST in modeling the PSF aberrations in focus across its wide and fast f/1.2 beam.

3.3 Analysis of deep Subaru prime focus imaging

We now proceed to the analysis of actual data on the sky which is used in the cosmographical study later in Section 4.1. This archival data set consists mainly of Suprime-cam 80 megapixel mosaic exposures in Lynx (α : 132.20, δ : +44.93) in the $[B/V/R_c/i'/z']$ filters for [60, 80, 90, 65, 90] minutes on the Subaru telescope during the first observing season in 2001 & 2002. The large format camera with a 30' field of view enables observation of tens of megaparsecs of structure at high redshift. Observation of the Lynx field with Suprime-cam were motivated by an excess of clustering at $z \sim 1.3$ found after photometric followup observation of an X-ray selected cluster (Rosati et al., 1999). Additionally, there is a strongly lensed galaxy which forms an arc around the massive foreground cluster at $z \sim 0.5$ which allows for X-ray and lensing masses to be compared (Fosbury et al., 2003). The abundance of clustering along the line of sight, both at medium and high redshift, provides a compelling reason to study the whole field with weak lensing measurements.

To image the large scale structure in Lynx, hundreds of mosaic CCD exposures were dithered during observation to provide a uniform coverage across the field. Raw images were reduced for

3.3. Analysis of deep Subaru prime focus imaging

Figure 3.3.1: AB magnitude histogram of all Suprime-cam detections (3 or more pixels above 3σ) in the Lynx field, showing completeness to $\sim 27th$ magnitude, enabling photometric redshift identification of sources at $z > 1.0$.

scientific analysis partially using the SDFRED1 data reduction process, which provides Suprime-cam image overscan and bias subtraction, flat fielding, atmospheric dispersion correction, as well as masking of known bad pixels (Yagi et al. (2002), Ouchi et al. (2004)). Reduced images are then astrometrically aligned using SCAMP (Bertin, 2006) by matching to known objects in the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) catalogs. The analysis pipeline must fork at the step of image combination, because two different criteria must be optimized for weak lensing and photometric analysis.

3.3.1 Photometric analysis

For photometry, all images in a given $BVR_c i' z'$ filter are PSF matched and coadded using the SDFRED1 pipeline. PSF matched photometry is then performed with ColorPro (Coe & Benitez, 2015), where we form a detection image using the deepest and best seeing frames in the R_c, i', z' (reddest) filters, weighted by depth. This detection image is then degraded to individual filters where the seeing is poorer in order to estimate the isophotal flux lost by the degradation. PSF stars for this process are chosen using the same method described below in the shape measurement section 3.3.2. The degradation of the images is performed using IRAF's `psfmatch` to determine the

3.3. Analysis of deep Subaru prime focus imaging

Figure 3.3.2: Left: z_{phot} vs. z_{spec} correspondence in the Lynx field, showing good calibration with a few outliers which can be filtered with quality cuts. The vertical band at $z \sim 1.3$ corresponds to the spectroscopically confirmed members of the high redshift super cluster containing Lynx-E, -W, and others. Right: dispersion of the left figure was measured to be $\sigma \sim 0.060$ for $z < 1.0$, implying very complete separation of foreground lenses and background sources.

kernel by which to convolve the good seeing images to ones of poorer seeing. This process results in a PSF-corrected magnitude that provides robust colors for faint and small galaxies which are close to the noise floor in images (Coe et al., 2006). The resulting photometric catalog is then zero-point calibrated using a combination of matching to SDSS data as well as stellar locus regression (High et al., 2009) to determine precise zeropoint magnitudes across the coadded images. See Figure 3.3.1 for the number-magnitude distribution galaxies in the Lynx field.

These well-calibrated zeropoints are essential to ensuring accurate photometric redshift separation of foreground/background objects in lensing scenarios. Our calibrated broadband galaxy colors are photometrically matched to models of redshifted galaxy spectral energy distributions (SEDs) using the Bayesian Photometric Redshifts (BPZ) software (Benítez, 2000), which provides estimates of the likelihood of redshift and type, $P(z, t)$, for every object. Some modifications to the defaults were made to improve the magnitude prior as well as updated galaxy SED templates which proved useful in the Deep Lens Survey (Schmidt & Thorman, 2013). These tweaks reduced the overall scatter and bias, resulting in $\sigma[(z_p - z_s)/(1 + z_s)] = 0.083$ for all z and $\sigma \sim 0.060$ at $z < 1.0$, as seen in Figure 3.3.2. The photometric redshifts are further calibrated for zeropoint

3.3. Analysis of deep Subaru prime focus imaging

offsets using hundreds of high-confidence redshifts from spectroscopic clustering surveying of the field (Mei et al., 2012).

3.3.2 Shape analysis

For weak lensing analysis, image quality must not be compromised via the above PSF equalization process, which degrades images to match the PSF of the worst seeing filter. We assure that the stacked detection coadds and image analysis for shear measurement take advantage of the best seeing exposures. The V/R/i images are of sufficient PSF quality for weak lensing. In each of these bands, non-PSF matched coadds are produced through **SWarp** (Bertin et al., 2002), and each image comprising the coadd is then individually analyzed. Preliminary object shape parameters are estimated in addition to the photometric measurements already computed. Stars for PSF estimation are then selected through a combination of filtering and clustering (Figure 3.3.3). First, since our field overlaps with SDSS we are able to identify the positions of spectrally confirmed stellar objects, likely including some fraction of binaries unsuitable for PSF analysis. We then use these stars to find the location of the PSF-like objects in our brightness/size diagram for each frame, allowing for non-spectrally confirmed PSF-like objects to be gathered. As discussed in Section 2.2.2 and Antilogus et al. (2014), this line is tilted due to instrumental charge transport (brighter-wider) effects. We then further require that these PSF-like objects occupy the 1σ region in color-color (all permutations of $BVR_{ci'z'}$) space occupied by the spectrally-confirmed objects. We also reject PSF outliers in $e_1 - e_2$ PSF ellipticity space. Objects which pass these criteria are shown as green dots in Figure 3.3.3.

The pattern of orientation and ellipticity shown in the whisker plot of Figure 3.3.4 is indicative of misalignment and drifting of optical elements during the exposure. Therefore, we model the dozens of PSF stars on each CCD chip and hundreds in each exposure with principal component analysis (PCA) to find the coefficients of twenty “eigenPSFs” for each. We then fit a polynomial surface to the PCA coefficients to provide a map of the PSF across the focal plane for each exposure, as in Jee et al. (2007). Figure 3.3.4 illustrates the PSF model fitting and interpolation, where special care has been given to ensuring the edges of each chip are roughly continuous and unaffected by gaps in PSF data.

Once the PSF stars have been selected and modeled in each frame, the process of forward PSF

3.3. Analysis of deep Subaru prime focus imaging

Figure 3.3.3: Choosing stars in each exposure to use for PSF modeling. All detected objects, stars and galaxies, are shown as small black points. Stars occupy the nearly vertical strip at the size of the PSF, and are for the most part much brighter and smaller than galaxies. The magnitude and flux radius of objects reported as stars in the SDSS are shown as blue points. By performing a flexible clustering analysis on these SDSS stars we are left with (red points). We additionally require that our PSF stars lie inside 1σ contours in the color-color stellar locus and the 2-component shear plane, which further purifies the stellar sample (green points/lines) and allows identification of aberrations as seen in Figure 3.3.4.

3.3. Analysis of deep Subaru prime focus imaging

Figure 3.3.4: The observed (red) and PCA model (grey) of shear of PSF stars in one exposure before PSF correction. Ellipticity patterns induced by both telescope drift and optical aberrations are visible at the few percent level. Bright stars which were chosen for PSF modeling but which exhibited blooming (the outlier red whiskers) were rejected from the polynomial PCA coefficient modeling and interpolation.

3.3. Analysis of deep Subaru prime focus imaging

Figure 3.3.5: The contours of the e_1 (left) and e_2 (right) components of the shear in the R_c filter compared to V, z' and i' filters. Broad agreement between filters indicates usefulness of the shape catalogs at all wavelengths. Small offsets, general oblateness along the $e=0$ directions presumably due to objects that had $e_1=0$ (a common feature of a pixelization-biased shear catalog).

convolution and shape estimation of galaxy images can begin. The shape measurement algorithm used in this study operates on each exposure and is a modified form of the one used in the DLS (Jee et al., 2016) called `sFIT` which won the GREAT3 gravitational lensing challenge (Mandelbaum et al., 2015). For each galaxy the algorithm fits an elliptical Gaussian jointly across all exposures, convolved with the spatially resolved PSF extrapolated to the position of the galaxy in each frame.

As a consistency check, we investigate the agreement between wavelength bands. The consistency between bands implies that the weak lensing analysis can be improved ultimately by combining the information contained in multiple bands. For our shape estimation, each galaxy has its own shape measured in three bands, each of which is determined from the `sFIT` algorithm using PSF stars in that band's exposures. The shape agreement between bands is then used to provide an estimate of the error on shape measurement, which is then used as a weight in later analysis including mass mapping and correlation function measurements.

Chapter 4

From Pixels to Cosmic Cartography: Using both E- and B-modes to Map Large Scale Structure

Weak lensing is a phenomenon which has been turned into a powerful tool measure the Universe's properties. Once measurements of galaxy shapes have been catalogued, their ellipticities can be used to infer shear and thus mass along the line of sight. Maps of the mass can be formed using the shears by taking the tangential shear around each point in the sky and filtering (or weighting) it. An example of this map can be seen in Figure 4.0.1, where galaxy ellipticities are shown as whiskers overlaying a map of mass along the line of sight.

The radial weighting function used to filter the tangential shear and infer the mass can be physically motivated or signal motivated. Physically motivated filter functions use the linear relationship between mass and photon bending angle to relate the shear γ to surface mass density κ :

$$\gamma(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int D(\boldsymbol{\theta} - \boldsymbol{\theta}'_0) \kappa(\boldsymbol{\theta}') d^2\theta \quad (4.0.1)$$

where the kernel D is defined to be:

$$D(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \frac{-1}{(\theta_1 - i\theta_2)^2} \quad (4.0.2)$$

Figure 4.0.1: Wide angle view of galaxy mass clustering and its detection with tangential shear. The relationship of shear to enclosed mass can be seen by eye as whiskers which are preferentially oriented tangential to mass overdensities in red. Each whisker corresponds to the average ellipticity of thousands of background galaxies, and a shear of 10% ($\epsilon = 0.1$) corresponds to a stick length of 2 degrees. The shading corresponds to mass which has been summed along the line of sight in steps of 0.2 degrees, where blue to red corresponds to summed masses 1×10^{14} to $M = 2 \times 10^{15} M_{\odot}$. Black contours represent a filtered version of the tangential shear around each point, showing clear detection of mass using a broad filter Q shown in Figure 4.0.2. The entire field shown is just one piece of a large N-body simulation, and the green box indicates the region which is further studied in Section 4.2.

This can be inverted with Fourier transforms to define a κ -map in terms of the observed shears:

$$\kappa(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \kappa_0 = \frac{1}{\pi} \int \Re[D^*(\boldsymbol{\theta} - \boldsymbol{\theta}')\gamma(\boldsymbol{\theta}')]d^2\theta' \quad (4.0.3)$$

where the constant κ_0 is inserted due to the so-called mass sheet degeneracy which results from the inability of local measurements to constrain globally uniform mass density. In practice, the kernel D is truncated far from infinite radial distances and is limited by the finite size of observation fields which apodize on the order of arcminutes to degrees. Additionally, to prevent the intrinsic ellipticity noise of source galaxies being amplified at small radii, the filter usually downweights shears near $\theta \sim 0$.

The physical nature of κ is useful in relating shear to mass, but from the point of view of optimal filters it is not the best way to detect mass with shear. A different kernel Q can be used in place of D in Equation 4.0.2 which can similarly be applied on shears inside of apertures but does not physically correspond to mass density. One such statistic is the aperture mass statistic M_{ap} first introduced in Schneider (1996):

$$M_{ap}(\theta) = \int Q(|\theta|)\gamma_t(\theta)d^2\theta \quad (4.0.4)$$

This function takes the background galaxy shears around each point in a map and filters them with the filter function Q . The optimal filter which will maximize a noisy lensing signal is exactly the form of the expected tangential shear induced by the characteristic NFW mass profiles as given in Wright & Brainerd (2000). This NFW profile is motivated by N-body simulations and theories of the formation of large scale structure which show that the clumping of matter forms in a hierarchical manner exhibiting a well-defined and characteristic mass density profile for groupings and clusters of galaxies (Navarro et al., 1997). The NFW tangential shear profile can then be approximated as an apodized combination of exponentials and hyperbolic tangent functions which can be scaled to profiles of varying mass and lensing efficiency. This useful approximately-NFW filter function was first introduced in Schirmer et al. (2007), and is given by Equation 4.0.5.

$$Q_{NFW}(x) = Q_{box}(x) \frac{\tanh(x/x_c)}{x/x_c} \quad (4.0.5)$$

Figure 4.0.2: The apodization of the tangential shear of a massive foreground cluster. This function is defined as Q in Equations 4.0.5 and 4.0.6, and is used to filter tangential shears and form maps of signal to noise as in Equation 4.0.7.

The parameter x is a dimensionless radius: the angular separation in units of the cutoff radius r_{out} , i.e. $x := r/r_{out}$, and x_c is a dimensionless parameter that controls the rate of tangential shear decrease (concentration) in the NFW profile, and is taken to be $x_c \sim 0.15$. The apodization function Q_{box} provides the exponential damping around zero radius and around the cutoff radius r_{out} and is given by:

$$Q_{box}(r) = (1 + e^{6-150r/r_{out}} + e^{-47+50r/r_{out}})^{-1} \quad (4.0.6)$$

The resulting form of the Q_{NFW} filter is shown in Figure 4.0.2.

Due to the mass-sheet degeneracy, convergence or mass density maps are measured by subtracting a reference shear from the measured shear, and thus are bipolar. Such maps are often thresholded at some positive level in order to display positive mass. Rather than picking thresholds or contours arbitrarily, we choose instead use aperture mass signal-to-noise ratio; significance of mass density peaks may then be readily assessed. We spatially map the aperture mass signal-to-noise S_t by dividing M_{ap} by the correspondingly apodized shape shot noise with an average RMS source galaxy shear of $\sigma_e \sim 0.3$. This denominator is equivalent to computing the statistic in a

4.1. Weak lensing in the Lynx field

field with no lensing, and can be represented discretely as:

$$S_t = \frac{\sqrt{2} \sum \epsilon_{t,i} w_i Q_i}{(\sum (\sigma_e w_i Q_i)^2)^{1/2}} \quad (4.0.7)$$

Peaks in this S_t map correspond to locations where the tangential shear is largest and most similar to an NFW mass profile, which most likely correspond to clusters or groups of galaxies in the foreground along the line of sight. If instead of tangential shear we insert cross shear (shown in the bottom of Figure 1.3.1, we can make maps of B-modes. These modes are not as readily identified with lensing potentials, as they are not produced by isolated lenses in well sampled environments. This has led to the widespread use of B-mode maps and correlations as indicators of systematic errors in measurement or observation. However, we show that they do contain information about the lens field, and therefore should not be used as a systematic error indicator but rather a signal in itself.

In the following sections we explore the E- and B-modes in 3-dimensional weak lensing via an end-to-end analysis of observational data together with corresponding 3-D simulations of the successive lensing of background galaxies by foreground structures. Identical processing (according to Section 3.3 is done for both data and simulations (presented in section 4.2), which begins from image data and proceeds through photometric redshift sample selection, shear estimation, aperture mass measurement, and analysis. We reconstruct the observed lensing peaks in the field by estimating their mass and redshift and placing equivalent clusters in the simulation. In this way we can match the observed shear to a sum of successive lensing potentials along the line of sight. Using the maps of the E-mode signal, made by filtering the tangential shear of galaxies around every point, we locate high S/N extended regions and associate them with a mass and redshift using the filtered tangential shear and the redshift clustering of galaxies along the line of light.

4.1 Weak lensing in the Lynx field

In this section, we use a small region of the sky imaged to the full LSST depth to study the weak lensing shear components induced by the abundance of clustering along the line of sight. The largest cluster in this field is Lynx North (RX J0848+4456), with a mass $M = 5 \times 10^{14} M_\odot$ and

Figure 4.1.1: Zoom into 10x7 arcminute subfield RGB image of the Lynx North cluster at $z = 0.55$, with mass map contours overlaid, where blue to red contours go from S_t of -3 to 8, as defined in Equation 4.0.7. The bands used are the i' , R_c , and V for the RGB colors, respectively. Structures of foreground red cluster sequence galaxies are often observed to correlate with the E-mode shearing of background galaxies (those with $z_{phot} > 0.8$).

redshift $z = 0.55$ (Holden et al., 2001). Additional super-clustering of galaxies at redshift $z = 1.3$ has been discovered through a combination of X-ray surveys and galaxy clustering (Rosati et al. (1999), Stanford et al. (1997), Mei et al. (2012)). These archival data were gathered from the Subaru-Mitaka-Okayama-Kiso Archive (SMOKA) system (Baba et al., 2002). Suprime cam observations are also supplemented by HST observations which provide a sharper view of a smaller area in the Lynx field.

4.1.1 E and B-modes in the Lynx field

The most massive structure in our field, the cluster Lynx North (previously detected and measured in Miyazaki et al. (2007) is detected at $S/N > 10$ in all three shape catalogs V , R_c , i' . The combined

4.1. Weak lensing in the Lynx field

Figure 4.1.2: The reduced shear measured azimuthally around Lynx North cluster ($M = 5 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot}$ cluster at $z = 0.55$), as measured in the $V/R_c/i'$ wavelengths for sources with $z_{phot} > 0.9$. A model of the tangential shear induced on lensed sources at a median redshift of $z = 1.1$ is shown in black. The cross shears (filled color curves) displayed also agree between the bands, showing an anomalously low cross shear on the smallest scales which is not present in a singular NFW model. Error bars are computed from an assumption of intrinsic shape noise ($.3/\sqrt{N}$), as well as from the sample standard deviation in each bin (s/\sqrt{N}), where no bin overlap or smoothing has been applied. An estimate for the Einstein radius of the cluster is shown as the vertical dashed line.

S/N map is shown in Figure 4.1.1, where contours colored from blue to red indicate S_t from -3 to 8. The contours indicate the complexity of the mass clustering in the field of view and overlay an RGB (i', R_c, V band) image of the region near Lynx North. Red sequence galaxies in this region, indicators of cluster membership, often underlie areas of positive S_t across the entire field.

As a consistency check, we investigate the agreement between wavelength bands on the cluster's tangential and cross shear profile, shown as colored lines in Figure 4.1.2. Also plotted in that figure is a model of the tangential shear of background galaxies according to an NFW profile with mass, concentration, and redshift of $M = 5 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot}$, $c = 4$, and $z = 0.55$. The thick shaded lines in Figure 4.1.2 represent the non-zero cross shear component measured in each filter, where their thickness is the 1σ width as measured in each bin and which are representative of the γ_t (thin line) errors. The same distribution of galaxies is used in the measurements of tangential and cross shear. The consistency between bands implies that the weak lensing analysis can be improved ultimately

4.1. Weak lensing in the Lynx field

Figure 4.1.3: Aperture mass (E-mode) map of the Lynx field, with blue, red, and green contours corresponding to the i' , R_c , and V band shapes, which are independently fit. Shot noise normalized mass mapping is performed using sources with photo $z > 0.8$, and contours range from $0 < S_t < 3$. Agreement of E-modes between bands reveals the large-scale clustering of mass in the Lynx field.

by combining the information contained in multiple bands. and the shape agreement between bands can then be used to provide an estimate of the error on overall shape for each galaxy. This multi-color shape consistency is used as a weight in the mass mapping and correlation function analysis. Mass maps can also be made for each filter and compared, and the maps for all three bands are shown as contours in Figure 4.1.3. They are correlated. Calculating the Pearson correlation coefficient using the E-mode maps in the V , R_c , i' bands gives $\rho_{R_c, i'} = 0.5156 \pm 0.0005$ and $\rho_{R_c, V} = 0.4789 \pm 0.0003$, where the errors have been estimated from bootstrap resampling.

As mentioned above, we also analyze a small region of deep HST ACS imagery as first presented in Jee et al. (2006), which has a different orientation, camera, optics, shape measurement scheme, and is free of atmospheric effects, reducing the possibility of systematic B-modes induced or contaminated by these effects showing up in the Suprime-cam maps. In that analysis, a shapelet

4.1. Weak lensing in the Lynx field

Figure 4.1.4: Comparing E- and B-mode maps of a portion of the Lynx field as observed from both the ground and space (the black boundary represents 3 HST ACS dithers). Top: the E-modes observed around Lynx-North, where purple shading and orange contours are the maps from the ground and space, respectively. Bottom: the B-modes, where blue shading and red contours are the B-modes from the ground and space. Both maps show general agreement despite different PSF conditions, shape modeling algorithms, and boundary sizes. The shading and contours in both the E- and B-mode maps range from $-1 < S < 4$.

4.1. Weak lensing in the Lynx field

decomposition method is used to measure the shear, providing a useful cross-check for our own systematics in the Subaru data. The HST shape catalog was used in the 3σ detection of two $M \sim 2 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot}$ members of the $z \sim 1.3$ super cluster Lynx-E and W, which have been well-studied and verified with Chandra X-ray analysis in addition to the weak lensing mass. We match this space-based shape catalog with the photometry provided by the Suprime-cam observations, and then map the E- and B-modes as was performed with the ground-based data. These space and ground-based shears are then compared, as discussed below. The HST imagery we analyze unfortunately does not cover the central region of Lynx North at $z \sim 0.55$, but its influence is easily observed in the shear field near the boundary. Indeed, the tangential shear about the coordinates of Lynx North (outside of the HST observations) is virtually identical with both the shears as measured in the Suprime-cam observations and the model shown in Figure 4.1.2. This implies a good signal in the mass mapping algorithm as well, which we describe in the next section. Overlays of the E- and B-mode maps from Subaru and HST are shown in Figure 4.1.4, showing good correspondence between the E- and B-modes. Notably, the effects of Lynx North can be seen intruding on the northern edge of the HST field, shown in red contours, as well as other clusters in the field. This space-based observation validates the shape analysis and mass mapping algorithm used in the analysis of the ground-based data, indicating that the maps are likely not biased on large scales by observational effects due to the atmosphere, optics, or shape measurement algorithms. As for the B-modes, though there is disagreement on small-scales the general agreement is also apparent in the correspondence between shaded ($B > 0$) and unshaded ($B < 0$) regions of the map.

4.1.2 Lens modeling of the E & B modes

To investigate further the origins of B-mode, we simulate these observations in a controlled way in 3D using the actual foreground mass distribution with a variety of simulated source galaxy distributions. Lynx North, as the most massive cluster in the observed field, is easily detected as an extended peak in the E-mode map, Figure 4.1.3, with $S_t > 10$ in each observed filter. There are also many extended regions of lower signal to noise peaks in the mass map which are also detected in multiple filters and which most likely correspond to foreground structures of lesser mass or lensing efficiency. We compute a $S_{t,sim}$ map for an NFW profile, using the mass as a free parameter and estimating the cluster redshift and concentration parameter from the data. This fitting is performed

4.1. Weak lensing in the Lynx field

Figure 4.1.5: Simulated and observed E-mode maps, shown as filled contours and lined contours respectively. Locations of detected halos in the field above $S_t = 2$ shown as empty black squares. The simulated and observed maps are highly correlated.

simultaneously for all peaks in the observed S_t map with $S_t > 2$. The mass is therefore estimated from the comparison of the simulated map and the observed map, and the redshift of the cluster is estimated from the histogram vs redshift of the foreground galaxy density along the line of sight. The concentration parameter is assumed from a mass-concentration relation in Duffy et al. (2008). We do this fitting simultaneously for $N_{clust} = 128$ E-mode peaks as indicated by boxes in Figure 4.1.5, which are correlated with foreground lensing clusters or groups of galaxies. Though some of these assumed peaks may not correspond to real halos, and the real halos may not have exactly NFW shear profiles, their strength, spatial distribution³, and number density above $M = 10^{13} M_\odot$ is similar to what is expected in similarly-sized fields (see Section 4.2 for application to Λ CDM N-body large scale structure simulations).

We then model the shear of all background ($\sim 1 \times 10^4$ galaxies with $z_{phot} > 0.8$) as being the sum of shears by all halos in the foreground. This is done by taking each background galaxy located in

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3-dimensional coordinate space RA/Dec/z and computing the total reduced shear g_{tot} as the sum of all the shears induced by the predicted foreground halos. The reduced shear of background galaxies around each halo is computed using the shear from a single NFW mass distribution (Wright & Brainerd, 2000). Input parameters include the mass, concentration, and 3-d positions of the lens and source (as well as cosmological parameterizations of $h = .68$ and $\Omega_\Lambda = .7, \Omega_m = .3$ which determine angular diameter distances). The total shear g_{tot} for each background source is then given by the sum:

$$g_{tot} = \sum_j g_j(M_j, z_j, c_j, \delta_r, z_{source}) \quad (4.1.1)$$

where the sum is taken over all halos, j which lie in the foreground of the lens and where δ_r and is the estimated angular distance between source and halo, and z_{source} is the photometric redshift of the source. The resultant reduced shear sums for each galaxy in the simulation can then be compared to the observed shears. Since the simulations are shape-noise free, the reduced shears in the simulation are mostly of an amplitude $g_{1,2} < 0.1$ in correspondence with the weak lensing limit being applied here. The correlation of shear components of the simulations and observations is weak but statistically significant, $\rho_{e1:sim,obs} = 0.084 \pm 0.004$ and $\rho_{e2:sim,obs} = 0.088 \pm 0.014$. Adding a shape noise (pre-lensing) broadens the $e_{1,2}$ distributions to the observed values degrades the correlation between simulated and observed shears.

The simulated shears can then be run with same aperture mass mapping algorithm as described in the previous section to produce simulated maps, and then compared to the observed maps. This spatial correlation is shown in Figures 4.1.5, 4.1.6, and 4.1.7. The correlation coefficient of the simulated E- and B-mode maps with the observed maps is $\rho_{E:sim,obs} = 0.83 \pm 0.02$ and $\rho_{B:sim,obs} = 0.22 \pm 0.01$, which can be seen graphically in Figure 4.1.7. The E-mode correlation is quite strong, as it should be because we have iteratively fit the foreground halos to match the observed tangential signature maps. The simulated and observed B-mode maps also have statistically significant correlations, but at a weaker level. This is because the B-mode amplitudes in our noise-free simulation are much smaller than those in the observed field.

If random shape noise is included in the forward simulation by introducing an rms noise into each background galaxy at an amplitude of $\eta_{rms} = 0.3$, it is found that that the $1-\sigma$ width of the simulated S_t and S_\times distributions nearly match the width of the observed S_t and S_\times distributions

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Figure 4.1.6: Simulated and observed B-mode maps, represented as filled contours and lined contours respectively. Location of Lynx North is indicated by the circle, and other subclusters are located as in Fig 4.1.5. By eye, there is a weak correlation between the contours and the shading, which is measured to be statistically significant. The generation of weak lensing B-modes by introduction of a pure E-mode field is apparent.

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Figure 4.1.7: The correlation between the observed (ordinate) and simulated (abscissa) aperture mass mapping pixels for the E- and B-modes. B-modes presented are with masking out the edges by 10% , which does not significantly reduce the correlation. The simulation included the full lens distribution and realistic galaxy positions. Addition of shape noise in the simulation broadens the B-mode distribution (see Fig 4.1.8) and slightly reduces the correlation.

as seen in Figure 4.1.8. In confirmation, when random shape noise is added, the Pearson correlation coefficient of the E- and B-modes ($\rho_{E:sim,obs}$, $\rho_{B:sim,obs}$) are lessened, but the correlation still remains statistically significant.

Beyond those induced by shape noise, there are other sources of observational B-modes at play here. The largest and most mundane source of B-modes are those induced at the boundaries of the aperture mass map, where pure E-modes can leak into the B-mode when aperture measures are used (azimuthal symmetry violation). These B-modes can be mitigated by padding the edges of the simulation or by limiting consideration of B-modes near the edges entirely. However, these edge B-modes are related to the strengths and locations of the lenses in the field, and therefore are not entirely noise. Another source of B-modes is the clustering of source galaxies, as discussed in Schneider et al. (2002) and Yu et al. (2015). These variations in spatial positions of galaxies leads to an asymmetry in aperture measurements of pure E-mode fields, and again are completely describable if the known positions of E-modes are known.

We can probe and eliminate these two galaxy density effects in a simulation by using a uniform distribution of galaxies at a fixed redshift which are lensed by the estimated 3D positions of halos. If we map the E- and B-modes using an extended uniform distribution of galaxies (at a single

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Figure 4.1.8: The distribution of E- and B-mode map pixel values. Red lines show the simulated shears of a uniform (homogeneous) source plane of galaxies at $z = 1.0$ that fill the observed field of view. Green lines use the actual (inhomogeneous) distribution of source galaxies, which with the addition of shape noise form the blue lines, better match the observed distributions (shaded). B-mode distributions are shown without edge effects, indicating the presence of multiple lensing B-modes in the uniform galaxy simulation.

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source plane of $z = 1.0$) such that no cluster is within several aperture radii of the extended galaxy boundary, the edge effect disappears and the correlation with the observed B-mode map is greatly reduced. However, as shown in Figure 4.1.8, there are still non-zero B-modes even in the case of uniform source galaxy distributions.

The B-modes which remain after edges and source non-uniformity effects are removed are perhaps more physically interesting, as they can be a sign of multiple lensing of background galaxies. For instance, the B-mode patterns induced by two massive cluster lenses projected along the line of sight produces an asymmetric quadrupole pattern as discussed in Bertin & Lombardi (2001). However, the simulated source galaxy density in their study was much higher than our current ground observations allow, and their simulations only include very fortuitous alignments of clusters along the line of sight. Therefore, we do not expect such obvious B-mode patterns in our observations, and they aren't readily seen in our observed maps. However, in our simulations we can probe this multi-lensing effect by modifying the distribution of lenses and galaxies. In fact, it is observed that the width of the S_{\times} distribution is broader in the case of realistic 3D lens positions than when all lenses are placed at a single redshift. Additionally, if the source galaxy density is greatly increased to $n_{gal} = 100 \text{ arcmin}^{-2}$, the width of the S_{\times} distribution is increased even further and the quadrupolar B-mode pattern of double lensing (Bertin & Lombardi, 2001) is observable in the maps. In practice, this multi-lens effect broadens the simulated (and observed) S_{\times} distribution by a small amount, but given the much lower surface density of $z > 0.8$ galaxies in our observations, the effect of double lensing in this field is unresolvable.

Finally, there are B-modes in the observed $V/R_c/i'$ maps which have larger amplitudes than can be accounted for by our lensing simulation. These stronger B-modes, shown as the excess of gray shaded area over the blue line in Figure 4.1.8, might be accounted for with more realistic simulation of the lensing potential distribution which we can only approximate. For instance, in the simulation we do not include void lensing, which would increase the number of negative E-modes and likely contribute positive and negative B-modes. Additionally, on the smallest and largest scales the finite field of view, our observations limit the size of E-modes which are measurable with our data, and this necessarily limits our E- and B-mode simulation which are constrained in this way by the observations. Lensing on scales less than $\sim 1 \text{ Mpc}$ and scales which span the entire field of view, those larger than $\sim 100 \text{ Mpc}$, are therefore unaccounted for in our finite field reconstruction.

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B-modes may be induced by lenses outside the field.

4.1.3 Shear correlation functions

Statistical correlations are complimentary to spatial maps. While losing spatial map information, the summary statistics produced by correlating the shears of all galaxies can provide a less noisy test of the origins of B-mode. Correlation functions over the field are computed using both the observed shears and those simulated under multiple conditions. The shear correlations ξ_{\pm} , the E- and B-mode aperture mass dispersion $\langle M_{ap,\times}^2 \rangle$, and tophat shear $\langle \gamma^2 \rangle_{E,B}$ dispersion are calculated on scales of $.5 < \theta < 15$ arcminutes. The raw shear correlation function is computed by correlating the tangential and cross shear around each galaxy, and either summing or differencing the two correlations.

$$\xi_{\pm}(\theta) = \langle \gamma_t \gamma_t \rangle \pm \langle \gamma_{\times} \gamma_{\times} \rangle \quad (4.1.2)$$

These raw correlations can depend on both the E- and B-mode power spectrum, and so the decomposition into aperture mass statistics is a useful one. We define the aperture mass correlations in terms of the ξ_{\pm} functions generally as:

$$\langle M_{ap,\times}^2 \rangle(R) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{r dr}{2R^2} \left[T_+ \left(\frac{r}{R} \right) \xi_+(r) \pm T_- \left(\frac{r}{R} \right) \xi_-(r) \right] \quad (4.1.3)$$

where M_{ap} and M_{\times} take the plus and minus signs, respectively, and the functions T_{\pm} are window functions which are generalized autocorrelations of the filter function Q , and which limit the inclusion of small and large radii which are difficult to measure. At the outset of this chapter we chose Q to be a signal-matched filter (NFW-like) for optimal detection of E-modes, but for the correlation functions presented here we use a Gaussian-derivative type window function which give T_{\pm} in the form:

$$T_+(s) = \frac{s^4 - 16s^2 + 32}{128} \exp(-s^2/4) \quad (4.1.4)$$

$$T_-(s) = \frac{s^4}{128} \exp(-s^2/4) \quad (4.1.5)$$

as presented in Crittenden et al. (2002).

Another popular cosmic shear statistic is the shear dispersion within a circle of radius R , which

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can again be decomposed into the shear-shear correlations as given by the expression:

$$\langle \gamma^2 \rangle_{E,B}(R) = \int_0^{2R} \frac{r dr}{2R^2} \left[S_+ \left(\frac{r}{R} \right) \xi_+(r) \pm S_- \left(\frac{r}{R} \right) \xi_-(r) \right] \quad (4.1.6)$$

where the E- and B-modes correspond to the + and - in the equation on the R.H.S. These E/B decompositions of the shear field are also filtered analogously to $\langle M_{ap,\times}^2 \rangle$, but with the S_{\pm} window functions applied as follows:

$$S_+(s) = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(4 \arccos(s/2) - s\sqrt{4-s^2} \right) \quad (4.1.7)$$

$$S_-(s) = s\sqrt{4-s^2}(6-s^2) - 8(3-s^2) \arcsin(s/2) / (\pi s^4) \quad (4.1.8)$$

for $s \leq 2$, and $S_-(s) = 4(s^2 - 3)/(s^4)$ for $s \geq 2$. These window functions are broader than T_{\pm} , implying that more shear dispersion signal is included but the signal is less localized. A constant shear generates contributions to both E- and B-modes (Schneider et al., 2002).

The correlations are computed on our dataset using the `TreeCorr` code (Jarvis et al., 2004), and the results are displayed in Fig 4.1.9. Three separate shear datasets are shown: the observed shears, those simulated with uniform source plane at $z = 1.0$ at a galaxy number density of 11 arcmin^{-2} , and those simulated using the observed $RA/Dec/z$ positions on the sky. E- modes for each statistic are the upper curves in each subplot in purple shades, and B-modes are shown in shades of aqua. Error bars on the observed correlation functions are from purely shape noise with an $\eta_{rms} = 0.3$, and the simulated cases have no noise added. As a null test, randomizing the shear components but keeping the positions fixed resulted in zero correlation in all statistics at all scales.

This field has extensive large scale structures which give an average matter density in excess of that given by the universal mass power spectrum. Thus the correlation functions as computed on this limited field reach large values, as expected from the depth of the field and the abundance of clustering along this line of sight. Interestingly, there are also non-zero B-mode correlations, which ordinarily might be blamed on incomplete modeling of the PSF or gaps in the data. However, there are B-modes of similar amplitude in each correlation function even when there is no masking and a uniform lens plane is used. This implies that the majority of observed B-modes are not due to a PSF modeling issue or even the clustering of source galaxies, but rather are intrinsic to these

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Figure 4.1.9: The three shear correlation functions for the Lynx field, ξ_{\pm} , $\langle M_{ap,\times}^2 \rangle$, and $\langle \gamma_{E,B}^2 \rangle$. The simulated approximation of the lensing in the field, estimated from 2-dimensional weak lensing maps, also captures the shape of the observed correlation functions. In each panel, for each correlation function, three different sets of shears are correlated: 1) the observed shears and positions (which are clustered), 2) the simulated shears (which are lensed by multiple planes) and observed locations (in RA/Dec and z), and 3) a uniform background of galaxies at $z = 1.0$ with the same number density as the observations, indicating the observed B-modes are not just due to source clustering.

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particular decompositions of a realistic shear field into E- and B-modes.

One may worry about the edges of this field, in that there seems to be B-modes induced at the boundaries of the field due to incomplete sampling of cluster-induced E-modes. However, since the correlation functions ξ_{\pm} are directly sampled at each galaxy point and not on a grid (as in the mapping scenario), the edges are not an issue (Schneider et al., 2002). In fact, masking more (~ 5 arcmin) of the edges of the observation does not noticeably change the correlation function.

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We describe the validation of our cartographic method using the N-body cosmology simulation Buzzard (DeRose et al., 2017). The Buzzard simulation provides Dark Energy Survey (The Dark Energy Survey Collaboration, 2005) 5-year depth catalogs that include positions (RA/Dec/ z) and reduced shear (g_1/g_2) of galaxies computed from ray-tracing (using CALCLENS, Becker (2013)), as well as the mass M_{200} and positions of clusters. Using this information we can test the ideas presented in Sec. 4.1.2, namely the applicability of the approximation in Equation 4.1.1, and as a check of whether B-modes are observationally present in the mapping of the simulation. The first of these tasks will require estimating the background galaxy shears using the known locations of cluster masses. Then the B-modes observed in the simulation are presented and shown to correlate with those estimated from only the E-mode data.

Taking a small slice of the Buzzard universe, about a degree on a side, we find galaxies and clusters distributed in 3D fashion as shown in Figure 4.2.1. There is a large cluster centered in the foreground of this slice as $z = 0.28$ with mass $M_{200} = 6.8 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot}$ which will serve as an anchor for our observations. There are also ~ 120 other clusters with $M_{200} > 2 \times 10^{13} M_{\odot}$ which will also be used into the lensing simulation. If we then slice the galaxy catalog by choosing galaxies only with $z_{photo} > 0.5$ (as shown in Figure 4.2.1) we should be able to easily detect this foreground cluster, given $\sim 40,000$ background galaxies with an observed number density of $n = 13$ background galaxies per square arcminute.

We first test the approximation of the shear of each background galaxy as the summation of the shears induced by the most massive clusters along the line of sight. This approximation is quite robust in the weak lensing limit, and clear comparisons between approximated shears and

Figure 4.2.1: Three dimensional (RA/Dec/ z) distribution of galaxies (colored dots) and clusters (black circles) a small slice of the Buzzard simulation. Each side of the cube shows the projection of positions along two axes. All source galaxies above the redshift cut of $z > 0.5$ are lensed by all foreground clusters, enabling the locations of foreground clusters can be inferred from weak lensing analysis of the background sources. Much of the complexity in the nonlinear structure formation, which affects both the source galaxy and the foreground cluster density, can be recaptured in the 3-D lensing simulations which approximate mass and distance from the data.

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Figure 4.2.2: Comparing the shears as computed by **CALCLENS** and those from the re-simulation method described in the body. There is broad agreement between both the components of the shear, confirming the re-simulation’s usefulness. There is a slight offset in the field shear for the component g_1 which is seen in the ray-tracing and is captured in the re-simulation and is traceable to an asymmetry in the distribution of mass in the field.

those computed from ray tracing the Buzzard simulation can be seen in Figure 4.2.2. The broad agreement between both components of the shear indicates that the re-simulated shears are a good approximation to the ray-tracing ones, when given a catalog of foreground mass.

However, applying this technique to the sky necessarily means we must make our own catalog of massive clusters. In the observational frame, we are provided with measurements of the reduced shear (g_1/g_2) and RA/Dec/ z of galaxies, and must find clusters using any combination of these parameters. To show the feasibility of this method in the Buzzard universe (and therefore in the Lynx field and other surveys), we automatically locate clusters by finding peaks in the map of the aperture mass statistic and estimate the unknown masses and redshifts of the clusters from filtering the shears and through redshift clustering of foreground galaxies.

First, the peaks in the aperture mass map are located using an image segmentation process similar to that used in **SExtractor**. The resulting locations are shown in Figure 4.2.3. These assumed cluster RA/Dec positions are associated with measurable overdensities in the provided (but unused) halo catalog, but which can be approximated through the use of photo- z estimates of foreground galaxies along the line of sight. In this way, the masses are estimated from a combination of tangential shear profile fitting and correlations between observed M_{ap} signal-to-noise and M_{200}

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Figure 4.2.3: Segmenting the mass (S_t) map produced from filtering the Buzzard shears through the Equation 4.0.7 (S_t contours go from $1 < S_t < 4$). The boxes show the locations of detected peaks which will be fed into the mass measurement and re-simulation. Colored dots show the “unknown” locations of Buzzard halo catalog members with mass $M_{200} > 10^{13} M_{\odot}$.

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Figure 4.2.4: Estimation of lensing mass is performed through correlations between M_{ap} peak value, integrated S_t , and width (Eq. 19 of Schneider (2005)). The Buzzard halo catalog, which was not used in the detection or prediction on the abscissa, provides masses and locations which were summed in apertures of $150''$ to produce the actual lensing mass on the ordinate.

(Schneider, 2005). The resulting correlation between predicted mass and mass measured from the Buzzard N-body simulation is shown in Figure 4.2.4.

Using these predicted cluster masses and locations, which are proportional to the actual lensing mass, we then re-simulate the shear of the background galaxies as the summation of the predicted cluster mass lensings (thus introducing only E-modes into the shear field). Application of Eq. 4.0.7 on these shears produces re-simulated M_{ap} and M_{\times} (E and B-mode) maps which we can compare to the ones which utilize ray-tracing shears as seen in Figure 4.2.5. Both maps illustrate the presence of B-modes with realistic distributions of clusters and source galaxies. The overestimation of lensing mass seen in Figure 4.2.4 leads to a slight over-estimation of S_t and S_{\times} , however the overall pattern is seen to be correlated. The shear correlation functions can also be computed on this narrow region of the simulated sky, which can be seen in Figure 4.2.6 and appear to have similar shape and scale.

The similarity between the two sets of shears, as re-simulated from the sum of lenses along the line of sight and those computed from ray-tracing an N-body simulation, represents an opportunity for a simplistic representation of observed shears as a sum of finite components. This method

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Figure 4.2.5: Comparison between the re-simulated and Buzzard ray-traced E- and B-mode maps, all colorbars are $-1 < S < 1$ white to black. In the left column, maps are produced from shear computed by summing the tangential shear of masses estimated in Figure 4.2.4 at the locations indicated by open orange circles. On the right, shear is calculated through application of CALCLENS multiple-plane ray-tracing algorithm through the Buzzard N-body simulation. B-modes are present in both maps at similar amplitudes and locations.

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Figure 4.2.6: The three shear correlation functions for the re-simulated shears as compared to those from N-body ray-tracing. Shear-shear ξ_{\pm} , aperture mass $\langle M_{ap,\times}^2 \rangle$, and top-hat shear $\langle \gamma_{E,B}^2 \rangle$ are shown in the top, middle, and bottom rows and defined in Eqs. 4.1.2, 4.1.3, and 4.1.6 respectively. In each panel the spatial correlations of the re-simulated and N-body ray-traced shears can be compared and found to be similar in amplitude, shape, and scale.

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applied in the analysis of the Lynx field shears helps explain some of the observed B-modes in both maps and correlations. These apparent observational B-modes, which are similar between the Lynx field and Buzzard simulations, can be seen from the combination of these analyses. Edge effects as well as inhomogeneous source galaxy positions lead to these apparent B-modes, which must be taken into account if the B-mode map is to be used as a test for systematics or new phenomena. It can thus be assumed that these B-modes are not systematic errors resulting from PSF estimation or shape noise (neither of which are included in these simulations), but rather from the nature of mapping and correlating shears of galaxies which are realistically distributed amongst, and then lensed by, an inhomogeneous 3-dimensional web of lenses.

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